

API Reference Model

Deliverable D2.1

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Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
ToC	Table of Contents
EC	European Commission
ETA	Estimated Time of Arrival
EU	The European Union
WP	Work Package
API	Application Programming Interface
DTLF	Digital Transport and Logistics Forum
eFTI	Electronic Freight Transport Information
eFTI4EU	Electronic Freight Transport Information for the European Union
IdP	Identity Provider
eID	Electronic IDentification
eIDAS	Electronic IDentification, Authentication, and trust Services
IT	Information Technology
CEF	Connecting Europe Facility
B2A	Business to Administration
B2B	Business to Business
REST	Representational State Transfer
RPC	Remote Procedure Call
SOAP	Simple Object Access Protocol
protobuf	Protocol Buffer
XML	Extensible Markup Language
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
YAML	Yet Another Markup Language
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
RSS	Really Simple Syndication
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol

HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
JWT	JSON Web Token
OAS	OpenAPI Specification
TIS	Technology Independent Service
IAA	Identification, Authentication, and Authorization
UML	Unified Modeling Language
WSDL	Web Services Description Language
SAWSDL	Semantic Annotations for WSD
WS-BPEL	Web Services Business Process Execution Language
BPEL	Business Process Execution Language
LSPs	Logistics Service Providers
CRUD	Create, Read, Update, Delete

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1. Executive Summary

Deliverable 2.1, the API Reference Model, represents a pivotal milestone within the KEYSTONE project, encapsulating the culmination of Task 2.1 under Work Package 2 (WP2). This deliverable is strategically aligned with the overarching objectives of the project, which aims to tailor standardised solutions, contribute towards the development of a seamless, interoperable, safe, secure and intermodal digital transport ecosystem across EU. The overarching goal of the project is to foster data and information sharing between enforcement authorities, their agencies and entities operating in the logistics sector (transporting goods and passengers), enhance stakeholder collaboration between them, reduce compliance costs, reduce the impact on the environment and improve safety, as well as possibly foster the acceptance of the CCAM solutions. The API reference model is the very first and paramount step towards developing a robust API standard that will be used by several entities and thus standardise the transport system.

The specific objective of Task 2.1 and D2.1 is to develop an API Reference Model tailored for interlinking a data producer and a data consumer. To achieve this, a comprehensive methodology has been meticulously crafted and followed, incorporating extensive literature reviews/interviews/meetings/discussions with professionals in the standardisation and data spaces domain that were carried out during the course of T2.1 (IDSA, DTLF subgroup 2, Datex II, NAPCORE etc.), stakeholders' needs assessments, platform evaluations, and insights, as well as assessment and consideration of all needs and requirements the WP1 has gathered and verified. The methodology also included thorough investigation, consultations and literature review gleaned from prior projects like FENIX and FEDerATED, especially for comprehending the Plug and Play Framework, as well as the semantic representation aspect, so in the end every end user may be able to define their own APIs and easily map their services without encountering programming/documentation issues.

Collaboration with domain experts and professionals from IDSA, NAPCORE, DTLF Subgroup 2, and others, as mentioned above, has been instrumental in deriving best practices and design principles for the API Reference Model. Key challenges and contributions of Task 2.1 include the definition, design, and development of the API Reference Model based on Plug and Play principles, ensuring interoperability and scalability.

The API Reference Model serves as a critical bridge between conceptualization and implementation, informing subsequent tasks within WP3 and Task 2.3 of WP2. By establishing standardized frameworks and methodologies, D2.1 paves the way for the design and development of functional web app interfaces, cybersecurity protocols, and API standardization efforts.

As the project progresses, the API Reference Model will evolve into the API standard, in the context of Task 2.3, further refined through iterative processes informed by real-world piloting experiences and stakeholder feedback. Intermediary outputs such as D2.3 and the final output, D2.5, mark significant milestones in this evolutionary journey, ensuring the continual enhancement and adaptation of standardized digital solutions.

Ultimately, D2.1 serves as the most crucial first step, a foundational cornerstone in the realization of a sustainable, efficient, and safe transport ecosystem at the European level. By facilitating seamless data exchange and integration, the API Reference Model contributes to the overarching goal of transforming the transport and logistics sector into a digitally interconnected landscape, poised for innovation and growth.

2. Introduction

2.1 Background

In the realm of European transport, the necessity for data-driven operations cannot be overstated. Real-time analysis and visualization of data concerning vehicles, drivers, and transported goods are pivotal for optimizing operations and ensuring compliance. However, the progress in this domain is hindered by various challenges, including legacy systems, fragmented data, capability gaps, and obstacles to data sharing.

Addressing these challenges head-on, the project Knowledgeable comprEhensive and fully integrated SmarT sOlutioNs for rEsilient, sustainable and optimized transport operations (KEYSTONE) has emerged with a bold vision. KEYSTONE seeks to contribute to a roadmap for the digital transformation of the European transport ecosystem by introducing standardized, truly Plug-and-Play solutions that bridge existing gaps, irrespective of legacy systems. This initiative marks a significant advancement in ongoing efforts to foster data-driven capabilities within transport operations.

KEYSTONE is designed to integrate existing data-driven platforms, services, and skill development solutions across a diverse spectrum of European stakeholders. Beyond technological advancements, the project also places emphasis on providing policy recommendations to alleviate shortages in data literacy and digital leadership. By fostering collaboration among regulators, operators, and service providers, KEYSTONE aims to harness the power of data for compliance purposes effectively.

Deliverable 2.1, the API Reference Model, is a pivotal component within the broader context of the KEYSTONE project's objectives. The endeavor to unify transport data across Europe requires standardized and interoperable digital solutions. D2.1 serves as a foundational element in this pursuit, providing a structured framework for API standardization that facilitates seamless data exchange among diverse stakeholders.

By creating the API Reference Model, D2.1 contributes directly to KEYSTONE's mission of bridging existing gaps in data-driven operations. It lays the groundwork for standardized communication protocols, enabling Plug-and-Play solutions that transcend the limitations of legacy systems. Moreover, D2.1 aligns with the project's aim to integrate existing data-driven platforms and services, fostering collaboration and interoperability across the European transport ecosystem.

As such, D2.1 represents a crucial step forward in the project's journey towards a resilient, sustainable, and optimized transport operation. It forms a bridge between the conceptual aspirations outlined in the project's background and the tangible implementation of standardized digital solutions. Through D2.1, the KEYSTONE consortium endeavors to pave the way for a future where data-driven operations drive efficiency, compliance, and innovation in European transport.

2.2 Objective of the Deliverable

The primary objective of this Deliverable 2.1, the API Reference Model, within the KEYSTONE project is to develop a comprehensive framework for facilitating seamless, interoperable digital exchange within the transport and logistics sector. This objective aligns closely with the overarching goals of the project, which include:

- **Contribution to Safety Standards:** The API Reference Model in essence serves as a blueprint for creating standardized data exchange protocols (the API Standard, that will be created in the context

of T2.3: Develop the API Standard) in the transport and logistics sector. Therefore, D2.1 paves the way for the creation of a comprehensive standard that will be tested in demonstrations in the context of WP4. By facilitating seamless and accurate information sharing among stakeholders, it enhances safety standards through improved enforcement and compliance measures. Thus, D2.1 directly supports the project's safety objectives by establishing a reliable and interoperable data exchange system.

- **Facilitation of Collaboration:** D2.1 is the cornerstone of the endeavour towards the development of the API standard that will implement the Plug and Play principles, thus the establishment of the necessary common framework that will enable the seamless exchange of data between logistics operators and law enforcement authorities and agencies. By enabling seamless data acquisition and sharing, it supports coordinated, data-driven solutions that improve the sustainability of freight operations. This fosters true collaboration, as companies can work with public authorities to optimize logistics activities, comply with regulations, and improve freight management. The model's implementation in pilots will verify its effectiveness in enhancing data sharing agreements and improving collaboration between private and public sectors, ultimately contributing to better decision-making and performance in urban freight management.
- **Reduction of Compliance Costs:** One of the key objectives of D2.1 is to contribute to the reduction of compliance costs associated with data exchange in the transport and logistics sector. By creating an appropriate reference model, the project may then proceed with its utilisation in standardising APIs based on it. The API Reference Model will define the API standard, which in its turn will become the necessary tool for the involved stakeholders to connect with each other and streamline information sharing processes, leading to cost savings for industry stakeholders.
- **Promotion of Wide Replication:** D2.1 aims to promote wide replication of standardized digital solutions at the European level. By developing a robust API Reference Model and taking Plug and Play principles into consideration, at a later stage an equally robust API Standard can be defined, which can be adapted and implemented across diverse contexts, and in particular for the actors to retrieve and send information between their own systems, 3rd party applications and the app developed in the context of WP3. Especially with the Plug and Play principles implemented, the scalability, flexibility, usability and integration capability of each API deriving from the standard will be enhanced. Therefore, the deliverable lays the groundwork for scalable and sustainable digital infrastructure within the transport and logistics domain and can play a transformative role in the endeavour towards true, secure and seamless digital transport ecosystem.
- **Development of an API standard that implements Plug and Play design principles:** The API Reference Model serves as a foundational component in achieving this objective, providing the framework for seamless integration and interoperability among digital systems and platforms. D2.1 contributes to that since it defines the next steps regarding standardisation of data formats and protocols. In addition, it facilitates the API discovery through semantic representation and supports modular integration for true seamless plug and play functionality. It essentially promotes consistency, reusability and interoperability.

In summary, the objective of Deliverable 2.1 is to develop a comprehensive API Reference Model that supports the development of a sustainable, efficient, and safe transport ecosystem. By establishing standardized protocols and frameworks for data exchange, D2.1 contributes to enhanced safety, collaboration, cost efficiency, and scalability within the transport and logistics sector, ultimately advancing the overarching goals of the KEYSTONE project.

2.3 Contractual References

KEYSTONE stands for “Knowledgable comprEhensive and fully integrated SmarT sOlutioNs for rEsilient, sustainable and optimized transport operations”. KEYSTONE is a HORIZON Research and Innovation Action

(Call: HORIZON-CL5-2022-D6-02, Topic: HORIZON-CL5-2022-D6-02-03) and has received funding from the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101103740. The project duration is 36 months, effective from 1st of June 2023 and the end date is 31st of May 2026. The Granting Authority is the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (DG CINEA¹), under the powers delegated by the European Commission.

2.4 Interconnected Work Packages/Tasks and their outputs/inputs

In addition to the contractual references outlined above, Deliverable 2.1, the API Reference Model, is intricately connected to other work packages (WPs) and tasks within the KEYSTONE project. These connections play a role in shaping the development and implementation of the API Reference Model and ensuring its alignment with the specific project objectives.

In the context of Deliverable 2.1, the Gap Analysis and State of the Art conducted in Work Package 1 (WP1) provided the necessary input and insights that inform the development of the API Reference Model. In particular:

- **Task 1.1 - Stakeholders' Definition and Needs Analysis:** This task focuses on mapping and analyzing stakeholders, their needs, regulations, and challenges related to the deployment of a digitalized transport ecosystem. The outcomes of Task 1.1, documented in Final Output D1.1: Stakeholders' identification and needs (Sabino Metta, 2023), provide valuable insights into the requirements and expectations of stakeholders regarding data exchange and interoperability. These insights serve as foundational knowledge for designing the API Reference Model in D2.1, ensuring that it addresses the identified needs and challenges of key stakeholders.
- **Task 1.2 - State of the Art Analysis and Requirement Generation:** Task 1.2 involves understanding the current state of the art in transport operations and capturing requirements for the KEYSTONE solutions through focus groups. The final output of this task, D1.2: Focus groups report including stakeholder requirements and expectations (Alexeis Garcia-Perez, 2024), includes stakeholders' requirements and expectations, which are instrumental in defining the functionalities and specifications of the API Reference Model. By aligning the API Reference Model with stakeholders' requirements identified in Task 1.2, D2.1 ensures relevance and usability in real-world scenarios.
- **Task 1.3 - Study of Existing Digital Platforms and Gap Analysis:** Task 1.3 conducts an in-depth analysis of existing digital platforms and identifies gaps between stakeholders' needs and current platform capabilities. The findings from this task, documented in Final Output D1.3: Needs and requirements for the future digital logistics ecosystems (Camille Leotta D. M., 2024), provide insights into the requirements for the future digital logistics ecosystem. These insights help shape the design and features of the API Reference Model in D2.1, ensuring that it addresses the identified gaps and requirements for seamless data exchange and interoperability.
- **Task 1.4 - Digital Ecosystem private and public perspectives:** This task generated use cases derived from transport ecosystems to define the interface and functionality of the KEYSTONE Digital Ecosystem. While Task 1.4 is not directly linked to D2.1, its outcomes contribute to the overall understanding of the digital ecosystem within which the API Reference Model operates, indirectly informing its design and implementation.

By leveraging the outputs and insights from these tasks within WP1, Deliverable D2.1, the API Reference Model, is developed with a comprehensive understanding of stakeholder needs, state-of-the-art practices, existing platform capabilities, and the broader digital ecosystem context. By taking into account such insights it is ensured that D2.1 aligns with project objectives and contributes effectively to the digital transformation of the European transport ecosystem envisioned by the KEYSTONE project.

¹ Official website of DG CINEA: https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/index_en

In its turn, T2.1 and the API Reference Model presented in this document, provides valuable input to other WP and tasks in the KEYSTONE project:

- Task 2.2 - Retrieving and sending enforcement data with the API Reference Model: Task 2.2 builds upon the API Reference Model created in Task 2.1 to focus on retrieving and sending enforcement data. It elaborates on specific parts of the model, such as interconnectivity with other platforms, information retrieval based on legislative requirements, and information exchange between vehicles and platforms. The outputs of Task 2.1 inform the methodology and abstract parts of the model developed in Task 2.2, ensuring consistency and alignment with project objectives. Special focus is also being made on the authentication and authorisation mechanism.
- Task 2.3 – Develop the API standard: this directly utilizes the API Reference Model developed in Task 2.1 to develop the API standard. This task involves implementing a library in Python using the Reference Model and addressing the connections identified in Task 2.2. The API standard, which forms the basis for interoperability and data exchange, relies on the foundational work of Task 2.1 to ensure compatibility with industry standards and stakeholder requirements.
- Task 2.4 – Definition of business models and business case: Task 2.4 leverages the outcomes of Task 2.1, among all the other relevant outcomes of other WP and tasks, to define the business models and business cases behind the Plug-and-Play solutions. The API Reference Model provides essential insights into the technological developments and standards established in Task 2.1 and will serve as basis for future developments in WP2 and WP3, thus making the reference model an excellent integral starting point for shaping the business models proposed by KEYSTONE. By understanding the technical capabilities and implications, Task 2.4 can start evaluating the economic and financial viability of the proposed solutions and integrate them into comprehensive business cases.
- Work Package 3 (WP3) - Toward Plug-and-Play Implementation: WP3 focuses on the design and development of functional web app interfaces and backends for real-world piloting. The API Reference Model provided in D2.1, along with the standard that will be developed based on that (D2.3 and D2.5) inform the development of APIs and data exchange protocols within WP3, ensuring compatibility and adherence to standardized practices. Additionally, D2.1 in conjunction with D2.2 contributes to cybersecurity protocols and API standardization findings applied in WP3, facilitating secure communication and interoperability within the transport ecosystem.
- Work Package 4 (WP4) - Piloting: WP4 focuses on piloting the solutions developed within the KEYSTONE project in real-world scenarios, as per the use cases outlined in D1.4. The API Reference Model from D2.1 serves as the foundation for data exchange and interoperability in these pilot implementations, as will D2.3 and D2.5 in the future. D2.1 paves the way towards providing standardized APIs and interoperability guidelines, and thus paves a way towards enabling seamless integration and collaboration between different stakeholders and systems involved in WP4 pilots.
- Work Package 5 (WP5) - Evaluation, Guidelines and Ethical Impact: WP5 assess the project through a series of KPIs. The API Reference Model provides the base for the Plug and Play implementation with certain indicators about the performance of the platform that will ensure the success of the project.

3. Literature Review – Relevant Projects

The role of freight transport and logistics is paramount for enhancing the competitiveness of the European economy and fostering social cohesion across all regions of the European Union. Over the years, the European Union has actively supported infrastructure projects aimed at creating a unified European market and enhancing the efficiency of goods and people movement, primarily through initiatives like the trans-European transport networks (TEN-T)² (Council, 2013).

However, in this dynamic business environment, the logistics industry faces a myriad of challenges that impact efficiency, compliance, and safety. WP1 has identified the most prominent ones through a series of focus groups, interviews and via the dissemination of a dedicated survey and collection of responses from numerous stakeholders from across multiple Member States of the European Union. One of the primary challenges highlighted is regulatory fragmentation and inconsistencies within the logistics sector. Despite efforts to harmonize regulations, disparities persist among member states, complicating cross-border operations and digitalization efforts. Furthermore, the fragmented nature of the technological landscape poses integration and interoperability challenges, hindering operational efficiency and agility. Additionally, the digital divide between large corporations and SMEs exacerbates disparities in technological adoption, while concerns about data security and privacy loom large in an increasingly digitized environment. Collaborative efforts between industry stakeholders, technology providers, and government agencies are essential to bridging this divide and promoting inclusive technological adoption. Lastly, great challenges derive from the field of sustainability and protection of the environment, such as air pollution from heavy-duty vehicles and the need for sustainable and efficient freight transport persist, prompting legislative action and digitalization efforts.

In recent years, the European Commission has introduced measures emphasizing sustainability and promoting intermodal transport to address these challenges. It has also financed or co-financed projects and initiatives, such as the projects FENIX³, FEDeRATED⁴, and eFTI4EU⁵ which have played, and are still playing a significant role in advancing the state of the art in the digital transport ecosystem. These initiatives have focused on enhancing data exchange, improving enforcement mechanisms, and facilitating the transition to electronic documents and automated control processes. In addition, leveraging insights not just from projects but also from the Digital Transport and Logistics Forum (DTLF)⁶, we aim to build upon their successes and lessons learned to promote regulatory alignment, standardization, and interoperability and specifically pave the way towards implementing and adapting the Plug-and-Play principles, thus contributing to achieving the EU-wide vision: that of paperless transport.

As the development of the API Reference Model within the KEYSTONE project is embarked upon, it is essential to recognize the valuable lessons learned and technologies developed by these pioneering initiatives and the involved experts. By leveraging their work and building upon their successes, the KEYSTONE project aims to develop a robust API model that addresses the evolving needs of the freight transport sector.

² The TEN-T is a European Policy that aims to develop coherent, efficient, multimodal, and high-quality transport infrastructure across the EU. More information can be found here: https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-themes/infrastructure-and-investment/trans-european-transport-network-ten-t_en

³ More information about the FENIX project can be found here: <https://fenix-network.eu>

⁴ More information about the FEDeRATED project can be found here: <https://www.federatedplatforms.eu>

⁵ More information about the eFTI4EU project can be found here: <https://efti4eu.eu/>

⁶ The Digital Transport and Logistics Forum, DTLF, is an expert group of the European Commission bringing together public and private stakeholders from various transport and logistics communities to support the European Commission in promoting the digital transformation of the transport and logistics sector. More information can be found here: https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-themes/digital-transport-and-logistics-forum-dtlf_en

In this **chapter**, we provide a literature review of key projects such as FEDeRATED and FENIX, which have significantly shaped our understanding of **their** principles in the context of transport and logistics interoperability. These initiatives offered critical insights into semantic and technical interoperability, decentralized data sharing, and **the design of federated platforms**, as documented in their respective semantic models, reference architectures, and technical specifications. The review **presents** these frameworks **for their respective goals and highlights the foundational principles they offer to the field at a high level. Moreover, the way these frameworks will inform the development of the API Reference Model and consequently the API Standard, which will be outlined in deliverables Deliverable 2.3 and Deliverable 2.4, as well as the adaptation of the Plug-and-Play principles, are further detailed in Section 6.2.**FEDeRATED

The FEDeRATED project, co-funded by the European Commission's Connecting Europe Facility (CEF), aimed to address the challenges of fragmented data sharing solutions in the logistics sector. Running until December 29, 2023, FEDeRATED sought to overcome the limitations of existing standards, platforms, and IT solutions, which hindered seamless data exchange. To this day, this project keeps on cross-fertilising projects and initiatives, as their developments showed great potential and KEYSTONE couldn't overlook such a project and such outcomes.

One of the key objectives of FEDeRATED was to establish a federated network of platforms that would enable harmonized data interoperability for multimodal freight transport transactions and regulatory compliance. To achieve this, the project developed a semantic model based on semantic web standards, providing a common framework for data exchange (Mulder, FEDeRATED Semantic Model in simple terms Delft Workshop29032022, 2022) (Mulder, Progress of the FEDeRATED Semantic Modelling Group, 2021) (Consortium, 2023) (Buwalda, 2023).

Furthermore, FEDeRATED focused on defining organizational, functional, and technical specifications for the federated network of platforms under real-life operational conditions. By collaborating with relevant stakeholders, including standardization bodies, software developers, and platform providers, the project aimed to validate the federative network across various EU transport Core Network Corridors (Roeland Van Bockel, 2021).

At the core of FEDeRATED's approach was the development of a digital twin, a comprehensive digital representation of physical infrastructure and transport objects. This digital twin, based on semantic web technology, provided a hierarchical structure for organizing real-world transport elements and activities, enabling stakeholders to understand and share data effectively.

Moreover, FEDeRATED emphasized the importance of semantic interoperability, which allows stakeholders to communicate and collaborate without the burden of traditional message standards. By defining a semantic model and categorizing events and business activities, FEDeRATED aimed to facilitate data sharing across diverse systems and platforms.

Key tools and specifications developed as part of FEDeRATED included the Service Registry, Index, Identity, Authentication, and Authorization (IAA), and Semantic Adapter. These tools supported functionalities such

as discoverability, security, access control, and data quality validation, laying the groundwork for a common, federated future in logistics.

The FEDeRATED project's achievements and methodologies can serve as valuable resources for the progress of the KEYSTONE project. Leveraging the semantic interoperability framework, tools, and specifications developed by FEDeRATED, the KEYSTONE project can enhance its own data sharing capabilities and promote seamless integration across the logistics ecosystem.

By adopting similar approaches to semantic modeling, event categorization, and tool development, KEYSTONE can facilitate harmonized data exchange, improve supply chain visibility, and unlock new opportunities for stakeholders. Additionally, lessons learned from FEDeRATED's implementation, including change management strategies and stakeholder engagement practices, can inform the development and deployment of the KEYSTONE project's solutions.

Moreover, the literature review on FEDeRATED and its work revealed that FEDeRATED, as a supportive project to the Digital Transport and Logistics Forum (DTLF), offers valuable insights into implementing Plug-and-Play principles, particularly relevant to WP3 of the KEYSTONE project, where application design takes place. FEDeRATED's focus on semantic interoperability and the development of tools like the Semantic Adapter align closely with the objectives of WP3 in KEYSTONE, which involves designing and implementing applications for seamless data exchange in the logistics sector. Plug-and-Play principles will be further elaborated in a following chapter, dedicated to DTLF (Digital Transport and Logistics).

Overall, the collaboration between FEDeRATED and the KEYSTONE project represents a significant step towards realizing the vision of a unified, digitally integrated logistics ecosystem, driving efficiency, transparency, and sustainability in freight transport and logistics.

3.1 FENIX

FENIX, the European Federated Network of Information eXchange in LogistiX, funded in part by the Connecting Europe Facility (CEF), aimed to establish a pioneering federated architecture for data sharing in the European logistics sector. Over a 48-month period, FENIX engaged 46 participants across 11 distinct Pilot Sites in the EU. The project's focus was on creating a sustainable federative network of platforms to facilitate Business to Administration (B2A) and Business to Business (B2B) data exchange among transport and logistics operators, ensuring interoperability across existing and future platforms (ATOS, 2020).

FENIX leveraged an interoperability-driven modelling framework, building upon previous outcomes from H2020 projects like AEOLIX⁷ and SELIS⁸. Each pilot site within FENIX aimed to establish integrated services using real-time Big Data streams for instant awareness and visibility, delivered from the cloud as a service. Key objectives included addressing fragmentation and connectivity challenges in ICT-based systems, interconnecting digital platforms, standardizing services, ensuring interoperability, and facilitating data sharing through digital corridor information systems.

FENIX's relevance to KEYSTONE, particularly to Work Package 2 (WP2) and Task 2.1 (T2.1), lies in its focus on interoperability, standardization, and data sharing within the logistics domain. WP2 of KEYSTONE aims to define the technical requirements and specifications for the API standard, while T2.1 specifically deals with the design and development of the API Reference Model, upon which the development of the standard will be based. FENIX's efforts provide valuable insights and best practices in addressing these challenges,

⁷ More information about the AEOLIX project can be found here: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/690797>

⁸ More information about the SELIS project can be found here: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/690588>

offering a blueprint for establishing interoperable data exchange frameworks and facilitating seamless connectivity among logistics stakeholders. Leveraging FENIX's outcomes can greatly inform the development and implementation of the API model within KEYSTONE, driving efficiency, transparency, and sustainability in the logistics ecosystem (Heide Buhl, 2020).

3.2 DTLF

The Digital Transport and Logistics Forum (DTLF)⁹ is an expert group established by the European Commission to facilitate collaboration and coordination between public and private stakeholders in the transport and logistics sector. With over 100 members from EU Member States' authorities, public entities, and private organizations, the DTLF works towards achieving full-scale digital interoperability and data exchange within the transport and logistics domain. Its main focus areas include providing technical assistance for implementing regulations such as the EU Regulation on electronic freight transport information (eFTI) (which poses special interest and relevance and will be investigated further in following chapter (UNION, Regulation (EU) 2020/1056 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 July 2020 on electronic freight transport information (Text with EEA relevance), 2020)) and developing a common data exchange framework to connect existing transport and logistics data sources and platforms. Through structured dialogue and expertise sharing, the DTLF aims to promote the digital transformation of the European transport system, enabling better visibility, real-time management of cargo flows, and reduced administrative burdens while fostering collaboration and sustainability.

Subgroup 1 of the DTLF focuses on transitioning transport operations from paper-based to digital formats, aiming to streamline information exchange and compliance verification processes within the EU. During the initial mandate (2015-2018), experts in this subgroup identified legal and technical obstacles hindering the adoption of electronic information exchange. Currently, teams within Subgroup 1 are collaborating on defining data sets, functional specifications, technical architectures, and certification rules for implementing the eFTI Regulation. This subgroup's efforts are crucial for realizing a paperless transport system and enhancing efficiency and security in transport operations.

Subgroup 2, known as the Corridor Freight Information System, addresses the challenge of interoperability and fragmentation in data sharing systems within supply and logistics. It aims to establish a common framework for information sharing in multimodal transport and logistics chains, integrating existing or emerging platforms into a federated network. This network enables seamless connectivity and data sharing among private and public stakeholders in a neutral and trusted environment. By developing technical specifications and implementation guidelines, Subgroup 2 is laying the groundwork for a federated network of platforms that promotes innovation, cost reduction, and addresses societal challenges such as safety, security, and sustainability.

Subgroup 2's focus on the Plug-and-Play concept is particularly relevant to WP2 and WP3 of the KEYSTONE project. WP2 aims to define the technical requirements and specifications for the API model, as defined in this document, while WP3 focuses on designing and implementing a web application based on these specifications. The Plug-and-Play concept, which enables individual stakeholders to connect and share data seamlessly according to common agreements, aligns closely with the goals of WP2 and WP3 in realizing the KEYSTONE project's objectives. Leveraging the insights and frameworks developed by Subgroup 2 could greatly inform the implementation of Plug-and-Play principles within KEYSTONE, facilitating interoperability and efficient data exchange within the logistics ecosystem.

⁹ For more information please visit: https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-themes/digital-transport-and-logistics-forum-dtlf_en

3.3 eFTI

Electronic Freight Transport Information (eFTI) is a digital framework designed to facilitate the electronic exchange of regulatory information related to freight transport and logistics among economic operators (such as transport and logistics companies) and between these operators and competent authorities. The primary goal of eFTI is to enhance efficiency, reduce administrative burdens, and improve the transparency and reliability of freight transport information across the European Union (EUR-Lex, n.d.) (UNION, Regulation (EU) 2020/1056 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 July 2020 on electronic freight transport information (Text with EEA relevance), 2020).

The movement of goods in the European Union has increased by nearly 25% from 1995 to 2015, with further growth predicted despite the recent slowdown due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The transportation of goods across various routes and modes (rail, road, sea, air) generates extensive information, traditionally exchanged via paper documents. This method, however, is inefficient, costly, and environmentally unfriendly (P. Chountalas).

Despite the availability of electronic document exchange solutions, the freight transport sector remains heavily reliant on paper-based systems due to:

- Fragmented legal frameworks causing inconsistent requirements for electronic documents.
- Non-interoperable IT systems and varied standards for electronic message exchange.
- Low acceptance of electronic documents among stakeholders.
- These issues result in high transaction costs, delays, and wasted resources.

The European Union introduced the Regulation on Electronic Freight Transport Information (eFTI) in 2020 to create a fully digital and harmonized information exchange environment. eFTI involves using digital technologies to manage and share freight transport information, including shipment tracking, customs clearance, and regulatory compliance.

The eFTI system involves several key stakeholders, including freight forwarders and logistics providers who arrange and coordinate the movement of goods and handle the electronic information exchange. Carriers, responsible for physically transporting goods, provide real-time updates on their status. Customs and border protection agencies ensure compliance with relevant laws and facilitate clearance for goods. Shippers, the owners of the transported goods, provide essential information about the goods. Government agencies set and enforce transport regulations and support the infrastructure and funding for eFTI. Lastly, technology providers supply the necessary technology and software to ensure the eFTI system is reliable, secure, and user-friendly.

The implementation of eFTI brings numerous benefits to the logistics industry by enhancing efficiency, visibility, and security. It reduces reliance on paper documents, cutting costs and minimizing delays, while automating and standardizing information exchange to streamline logistics operations. eFTI provides real-time visibility into the freight transport process, facilitating better tracking and tracing of cargo. It also supports compliance with regulations through electronic data exchange, such as electronic cargo manifests and consignment notes. Moreover, eFTI can integrate with other digital solutions like digital twins, smart logistics, and predictive maintenance, further advancing the digitalization of the logistics industry and enabling new business models and service offerings.

eFTI is envisioned to operate similarly to current digital waybills (e-CMR) used in road transport, where digital documents are accessed via mobile devices, streamlining communication and updates among connected

parties. eFTI is positioned as a crucial element in the digital logistics ecosystem, promoting real-time visibility, automation, and standardization, thereby improving overall efficiency, reducing costs, and enhancing security and compliance.

From August 20, 2025, all European Union Member States' competent authorities will begin accepting electronic freight transport information from economic operators. While it will not become mandatory for economic operators to use electronic documentation, the regulation establishes a legal framework to facilitate its adoption. This framework sets the conditions under which competent authorities must accept electronically provided regulatory information and lays down the rules for services related to making such information available electronically. This aims to organize the scene for widespread adoption of electronic documentation in the future, thereby improving efficiency and regulatory compliance across the Union (Camille Leotta D. M., 2024).

In conjunction with the regulatory aspect, several steps are being taken for the technical implementation of the eFTI and its adaptation requirements. The eFTI4EU project (Electronic Freight Transport Information for the European Union)¹⁰ funded by the Connecting Europe Facility (CEF) program of the European Commission, spearheads the implementation of EU Regulation 2020/1056 on electronic freight transport information (eFreight Transport Information). With a consortium of 22 partners, including nine Member States, the project aims to establish an efficient logistics network and promote freight transport digitalization through electronic information sharing between private operators and public administrations. By August 2025, following the regulation's enforcement starting in August 2024, certified eFTI platforms and service providers will be required to accept electronic information for control purposes. Currently, the project focuses on developing a unified technical architecture for eFTI, identifying data elements, and establishing standard models for electronic exchange. This initiative aligns with the eFTI Regulation's objectives and aims to create a harmonized and interoperable digital infrastructure for freight transport across the European Union, reducing administrative costs, enhancing control capabilities, and improving overall efficiency and sustainability in the transport sector.

eFTI4EU uses country-specific roadmaps to identify key elements such as requirements for national eFTI implementation, resource needs (both financial and technical), and the necessary specifications for the long-term operation of the eFTI exchange environment. The participating Member States identify existing systems, requirements for national eFTI implementation, resource needs, planned pilots, and long-term operational requirements for the eFTI exchange environment. This information will be documented in national roadmaps, serving as project plans for eFTI introduction. These roadmaps analyse strategic, organisational, technical, legal, and financial conditions in Member States to guide the development of eFTI gates according to EU and Member State requirements.

A work plan with the support of Member States will outline roadmap requirements, and a template will structure the roadmaps for harmonised data collection. The Roadmap Status Report will provide an overview of commonalities and differences in Member States, acting as a benchmark for harmonisation in the eFTI exchange environment, ensuring interoperability.

eFTI4EU relies on a good exchange between the EU Commission as the originator of the eFTI Regulation and the subsequent legal acts, and the stakeholders responsible for its implementation. The latter are mainly the Member States and their competent authorities, which are responsible for the implementation of the eFTI Gates, as well as interested economic operators that want to operate an eFTI Platform.

¹⁰ More information about the eFTI4EU project can be found here: <https://efti4eu.eu/>

eFTI and the eFTI4EU project are crucial to the KEYSTONE project because the eFTI provides the regulatory framework, standards, and technological impetus needed to achieve the project's goals of efficiency, compliance, interoperability, and innovation in the logistics sector. Integrating eFTI into KEYSTONE's Reference Model not only ensures alignment with current regulations but also paves the way for pioneering advancements in freight transport and logistics.

3.4 eID and eIDAS

In this section we provide an overview of eID and eIDAS, to lay the foundation for understanding the secure authentication mechanisms that are crucial for the operation of API standards, that will derive from the API Reference Model. eID and eIDAS principles ensure robust and interoperable electronic identification, which is vital for maintaining the integrity and security of digital transactions within the standardised APIs. By establishing a trusted authentication framework, eID and eIDAS facilitate seamless and secure access to services, thus enhancing user experience and compliance with regulatory standards. We recommend reading Deliverable D2.2 in conjunction with D2.1. D2.2 provides a very thorough, detailed overview into the practical implementation of the API reference model, focusing on retrieving and sending enforcement data, interconnectivity with other platforms, and information exchange requirements, and it specifically addresses the specific authentication mechanisms for APIs in relation to eID, ensuring that the theoretical foundations laid out in D2.1 are effectively applied in real-world scenarios. Understanding both documents is essential for understanding the comprehensive approach to secure, standardized, and interoperable API development in the KEYSTONE project.

3.4.1 eID

Electronic Identification (eID)¹¹ is a digital solution designed to verify the identity of individuals or organizations through electronic means. Issued by government authorities or authorized agencies, eIDs contain essential information about the holder, such as name, date of birth, photo, and tax code. They serve as digital proofs of identity, enabling secure access to services provided by both government entities and private companies.

eIDs allow users to access a wide range of services, including those provided by government and private entities, using a single digital identity. When a user connects to a digital service, they can use their eID to securely authenticate their identity. Compared to traditional credentials, eIDs offer a higher level of trust, ensuring secure and reliable access to online services, which aids in privacy protection and fraud prevention.

The authentication process involves three main steps. First, the user presents their authentication data, such as a username and password. Second, the system verifies the provided data against registered information. Finally, upon successful verification, the user gains access to the desired services.

A typical use case of eID involves a user accessing a service from a service provider who partners with an identity provider (IdP) to enable eID-based authentication. The process begins with the user visiting the service provider's website and selecting the desired service. The user is then redirected to the login page. Choosing eID authentication, the user opts for authentication through an affiliated IdP and enters their credentials. The IdP verifies the user's identity and redirects them back to the service provider with a positive authentication response, granting the user access to the chosen service.

¹¹ More information about eID can be found here: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/electronic-identification>

The benefits of eID include the convenience for users who can access multiple services using the same credentials without creating new accounts. Service providers also benefit from a secure and reliable authentication system.

3.4.2 eIDAS

eIDAS (electronic IDentification, Authentication, and trust Services)¹² is an EU regulation aimed at enhancing the security and effectiveness of electronic services and e-business transactions. Effective since July 1, 2016, eIDAS provides a common regulatory framework for secure electronic interactions among citizens, companies, and public administrations within the EU.

eIDAS establishes rules for electronic identification, allowing citizens and businesses to use recognized digital identification methods, such as electronic identity cards and mobile apps, across all EU member states. This simplifies cross-border access to services. Emphasizing the secure handling of personal data, eIDAS ensures that data is processed lawfully and transparently, respecting individuals' rights.

eIDAS introduces trust services, including electronic signatures, seals, and time stamps, which ensure the integrity and security of digital transactions. These services are legally valid and recognized across the EU. Additionally, eIDAS promotes interoperability among the electronic identification systems of EU member states, enabling the use of the same digital identity to access services in different countries.

To ensure interoperability, eIDAS requires each member state to activate its own eIDAS node, which connects national electronic identification systems. These nodes verify and validate digital identities and electronic signatures across borders, enabling full cross-border interoperability of digital identity systems.

The regulation establishes mutual recognition for eIDs issued by any EU country, provided they meet regulatory criteria and are notified to the Commission. This means that an eID issued in one member state is recognized and valid in all other member states.

eIDAS promotes a technologically neutral framework, facilitating cooperation among member states and ensuring seamless exchange of electronic identification data. This framework does not favor specific technical solutions, allowing for consistent and reliable cross-border transactions.

eIDAS enables European citizens to use their national eIDs to access online services in other EU countries. The eIDAS protocol acts as a bridge between national eID systems, ensuring consistent and reliable cross-border authentication.

A typical use case involves a user accessing an online service offered by a service provider in an EU country different from their own. The process begins with the user visiting the service provider's website and selecting the desired service. The user is redirected to the login page and chooses eIDAS authentication. The user is then redirected through the eIDAS node network to the eIDAS node of their country of origin, and further redirected to the IdP of the same country. After entering their credentials, the IdP verifies the user's identity and redirects them back to the service provider with a positive authentication response, granting the user access to the chosen service.

The benefits of eIDAS include a simplified user experience with seamless cross-border service access and enhanced trust and security in online services across the EU.

¹² More information about eIDAS Regulation can be found here: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/eidas-regulation>

To conclude, incorporating eID and eIDAS principles into the KEYSTONE project and specifically to its API Reference Model and the web app later on (WP3) provides numerous benefits, including enhanced security, interoperability, user convenience, regulatory compliance, centralized user management, scalability, data protection, and the integration of trust services. These elements are crucial for building a secure, reliable, and user-friendly digital service platform that can operate seamlessly across different jurisdictions and services within the European Union. Further information on the eID and eIDAS, as well as the implementation of such authentication mechanisms are also provided in more detail in the public deliverable D2.2: Retrieving and sending enforcement data with the API reference model.

4. Literature Review – APIs

An Application Programming Interface (API) is a set of rules and protocols that allows different software applications to communicate with each other. API is a middleman, letting developers use the features of a system, service, or application without needing to understand its internal workings. It is important to mention the three key points as follows: (What is an API?)

1. **Interoperability:** The use of APIs ensures the seamless interaction of different software components, fostering interoperability between diverse systems and applications.
2. **Abstraction:** APIs abstract the subtle complexities of a system, presenting a simplified interface for developers to interact with.
3. **Standardization:** A set of standards and conventions simplifies the development process for creating applications that smoothly utilize external services, thereby promoting efficiency and reducing complexities.

Figure 1 Application Programming Interface

4.1 Types of APIs

In software development, various types of APIs help systems communicate and work together smoothly, and specifically, some are referred to as: (Shepard, 2023)

1. **REST:** The Representational State Transfer (REST) is a distributed architectural style based on the architecture of the world wide web. The clients and the server are separate, which helps to establish a fundamentally distributed architecture and supports the independent evolution of the server logic and its clients. From a service contract perspective, this requires that a service offers one or more capabilities. Service consumers invoke a capability by sending a request message.
2. **GraphQL:** The GraphQL, originally developed by Facebook, is a Remote Procedure Call (RPC)-based protocol designed for large environments with high volumes of diverse types of data. It is a query language like SQL. It requires installed server-side and client-side software to carry out communication. Unlike standard RPC, GraphQL clients and servers commonly communicate over HTTP. The client and server have a copy of the JSON schema used to define and validate the data in an exchanged JSON message.
3. **gRPC:** The gRPC, originally developed by Google, is a protocol designed to support distributed systems with high scalability requirements. It provides a built-in authentication API with native support

for SSL/TLS¹³. A gRPC client sends a datum serialised into a hex value to the server as part of a protocol buffer (protobuf) message. The gRPC server processes the message and responds with a result also serialised into binary format as part of a protobuf message.

4. **Webhooks:** The Webhooks, which are HTTP callbacks set by users, facilitate near real-time event-based communication between applications. Activated by events in a source application, Webhooks utilize HTTP requests to transmit data to a specified URI in the target application. By eliminating the requirement for repeated polling, this method is gaining popularity for its seamless integration capabilities across diverse systems.
5. **SOAP:** The SOAP (Simple Object Access Protocol) is a protocol designed for the exchange of structured information in web services. By using XML for message format, SOAP provides strict standards and built-in features such as ACID-compliant¹⁴ transactions, security protocols and predefined messaging patterns. Despite a decline in its utilization, SOAP remains reliable for applications requiring strong typing, security, and reliable message delivery.
6. **WebSocket:** The WebSocket provides a persistent, low-latency, bidirectional connection for real-time data transfer between client and server. Unlike HTTP, WebSocket allows the server to transmit data to clients whenever needed, reducing latency, and optimizing resource usage. Despite potential challenges such as implementation complexity and limited support in specific environments, WebSocket is preferred for applications requiring instant data updates.

While REST maintains its dominance in the API landscape, driven by its simplicity, ubiquity, scalability, interoperability and ease of adoption, the rise of alternatives like GraphQL and gRPC is noteworthy. REST remains a reliable foundation, GraphQL provides tailored solutions for data optimization and gRPC stands out for its performance and language support. In contrast, options such as Webhooks, SOAP, and WebSocket, while useful in specific contexts, have limitations that may not meet the evolving demands of contemporary software development. Webhooks, reliant on HTTP callbacks, lack the structured query capabilities and flexibility offered by GraphQL for complex data retrieval and manipulation. SOAP, with its XML-based messaging and complex setup, may not align with the lightweight and fast-paced nature often required in modern applications. Similarly, while WebSocket excels in real-time bidirectional communication, its implementation complexity and limited support in certain environments may hinder widespread adoption. Considering all the aforementioned offers valuable insights for making informed decisions based on the unique strengths and trade-offs of each method, ensuring optimal choices align with the diverse demands of contemporary software development.

4.2 REST APIs

Based on REST architecture (The Postman Team, 2023) (What is a REST API?) (What is a REST API?, 2020) (Juviler, 2024), the client and server engage exclusively in a one-way communication process: the client initiates interaction by dispatching a request to the server, which reciprocates with a response. Notably, servers lack the ability to initiate requests and clients are incapable of providing responses. This ensures that all interactions are instigated by the client.

The communication of REST APIs occurs via HTTP requests, allowing for the execution of standard database operations like creating, reading, updating, and deleting records within a resource. For instance, a GET

¹³ SSL (Secure Sockets Layer) and TLS (Transport Layer Security) are cryptographic protocols that provide secure communication over a computer network, such as the internet. They are commonly used to ensure the confidentiality and integrity of data transmitted between a client (such as a web browser) and a server.

¹⁴ ACID stands for atomicity, consistency, isolation and durability. It describes a set of expectations that ensure any database transactions are processed in a reliable way, resulting in correctness.

request could be used to fetch a record, a POST request to initiate creation, a PUT request to perform updates, a PATCH request to perform partial updates and a DELETE request to remove a record.

The condition of a resource at any given instant, is termed as the resource representation. This data can be communicated to a client in any format, including JSON, HTML, Python, PHP, or plain text, while JSON is popular for its readability, and it is not bound to a specific programming language.

Figure 2 REST communication

4.2.1 Advantages of REST

REST APIs provide numerous benefits that foster their extensive acceptance and assimilation throughout diverse online ecosystems, such as: (Sandoval, REST vs gRPC: Advantages and Disadvantages, 2023) (Naeem, 2023)

- **Interoperability:** REST APIs are built on the consistent standards of the web, encompassing the same language, code, and architecture. Their remarkable interoperability enables easy interaction, synchronization, and integration with a spectrum of applications.
- **Flexibility:** REST APIs are equipped to communicate using diverse data formats. In essence, they can be modified to adapt to nearly any web application, regardless of its format, language, or architecture.
- **Scalability:** REST APIs are highly scalable, capable of seamlessly handling thousands, millions, and billions of data concurrently without any impact on performance.
- **Security:** REST APIs usually implement authentication through access tokens. These tokens, being unique, present a significantly higher level of difficulty to crack. Moreover, they can be reinforced with additional authentication methods, thereby doubling the security standards.
- **User-friendliness:** REST APIs stand out for their simplicity and ease of use, making them more user-friendly compared to other APIs. Getting to know the REST API is a quick undertaking, regardless of proficiency in web development and programming. It is intuitively designed and user-friendly, addressing to individuals without prior web development experience, as long as they acquire knowledge in languages like HTML, Python or JavaScript.

4.2.2 Disadvantages of REST

On the other hand, it is essential to acknowledge the REST APIs' drawbacks: (Sandoval, REST vs gRPC: Advantages and Disadvantages, 2023) (Naeem, 2023)

- **Advanced design complexity:** Despite being more user-friendly, designing a REST API can be more complex than other APIs, particularly for individuals not familiar with web architecture.
- **Web connectivity:** Any adjustment to REST API must be made exclusively on the web. Unlike HTML web files, for instance, it is impossible to edit the API without an internet connection. Connectivity is mandatory for even the smallest change.
- **Variable performance and flexibility:** The performance of REST APIs can be slightly lower than other APIs, depending on the servers and internet speed. Additionally, even though their architecture

is highly versatile, allowing synchronization with other applications, the development of this architecture is somewhat less flexible.

Despite REST APIs' unfavourable points, they are a must-have for web developers and companies worldwide. This is the API of choice for millions of companies and development teams, consequently providing access to countless opportunities.

4.3 GraphQL APIs

GraphQL, an open-source query language (Byron, 2015) (GraphQL), redefines web-based software development with its client-centric approach. It emerged as an alternative to traditional REST architecture, solving the issue of over-fetching by allowing clients to precisely request needed data in a single query. The GraphQL ecosystem thrives on its flexibility and efficiency, supported by major programming languages and libraries like Apollo and Relay.

Fundamentally, GraphQL utilizes a predefined schema, detailed in Schema Definition Language (SDL), as a model for data interaction between clients and servers. This schema, which can be implemented in any programming language, defines the types of queryable objects, their fields, and the relationships between them.

In GraphQL, an operation can be a query (read), mutation (write), or subscription (continuous read). This innovative method not only simplifies data retrieval, but also optimizes network usage, deviating significantly from the sequential requests inherent in REST architectures.

In summary, GraphQL's progress centrally involves combining numerous requests into one, retrieving only the necessary data, and empowering clients to specify their data requirements. Developers are drawn to its adaptability, efficiency, and compatibility with various programming languages, signifying a transformative shift in web-based software development compared to traditional REST architectures.

Figure 3 GraphQL communication

4.3.1 Advantages of GraphQL

GraphQL offers a multitude of advantages and improvements compared to REST APIs, as they are presented below: (The SK Engineering Team) (Eke, 2023) (Why GraphQL: Advantages and Disadvantages, 2018) (GraphQL: Core Features, Architecture, Pros and Cons, 2019)

- **Simplifying data retrieval:** GraphQL simplifies the process of acquiring associated data by allowing developers to retrieve aggregated information in a single query. Unlike REST API, which often requires multiple requests to different endpoints, GraphQL streamlines the process and reduces the data retrieval complexity.
- **Rapid deployment:** GraphQL's schema-based approach enables swift development by prioritizing schema definition over the implementation of multiple endpoints.
- **Avoidance of over-fetching:** GraphQL allows clients to specify exactly which fields they need in the response, preventing over-fetching of data. This level of specificity ensures that only the necessary data are transmitted over the network, reducing bandwidth usage and optimizing device memory space.

4.3.2 Disadvantages of GraphQL

While GraphQL presents numerous advantages over REST APIs, there are noteworthy disadvantages to consider: (The SK Engineering Team) (Eke, 2023) (Why GraphQL: Advantages and Disadvantages, 2018) (GraphQL: Core Features, Architecture, Pros and Cons, 2019)

- **Hard to sustain:** GraphQL can present difficulties in maintenance, primarily due to its complex syntax. Developers may find it more challenging to manage and troubleshoot compared to simpler alternatives.
- **Sensitivity to crashes:** Precise design is crucial in GraphQL, as even a minor mistake in the schema can lead to excessive database searches, leading to potential server crashes. This highlights the necessity for careful schema planning and execution.
- **Safety issues:** GraphQL presents potential security vulnerabilities as hackers can exploit queries to gain access to sensitive data from the server. Protecting schemas is crucial to prevent unauthorized access and data breaches.
- **Complex error processing:** Error handling in GraphQL might be less convenient. The generation of various error types can complicate the debugging process for developers, reducing ease of use in identifying and resolving issues.

As a final point, GraphQL proves to be an excellent solution for ubiquitous issues. It offers a simple and efficient approach to communicate with the server.

4.4 gRPC APIs

gRPC (A high performance, open source universal RPC framework, $\chi.\chi.$) represents a versatile and open-source framework designed to optimize cross-platform RPC. This framework utilizes protobufs, serving as an interface description language that enables disparate systems to execute remote procedures, regardless of their implementation, language, or process. Unlike REST, gRPC operates over HTTP/2, highlighting efficiency through lightweight messages and straightforward interactions.

Furthermore, described as a modern, high performance and open-source RPC framework, gRPC has a wide range of applications. It efficiently connects services within and across data centers, offering plug-and-play support for critical functionalities like load balancing, tracing, health checking, and authentication. Beyond data centers, it proves useful by connecting devices, mobile applications, and browsers to backend services, making it a comprehensive solution for various distributed computing scenarios.

Figure 4 gRPC communication

4.4.1 Advantages of gRPC

gRPC introduces several advantages that have fuelled its extensive acceptance and integration in various computing environments, including: (Sandoval, REST vs gRPC: Advantages and Disadvantages, 2023) (What is gRPC: Main Concepts, Pros and Cons, Use Cases, 2021)

- **Efficiency:** gRPC maximizes efficiency through the utilization of protobufs¹⁵ and the HTTP/2 protocol¹⁶, presenting a contemporary and streamlined methodology for RPC design.
- **Performance:** gRPC stands out in performance, demonstrating speeds that outpace traditional REST+JSON communication (What is gRPC: Main Concepts, Pros and Cons, Use Cases, 2021). Additionally, it achieves reduced message sizes, enhancing a more agile and responsive communication process.
- **Versatile streaming:** Beyond standard RPC frameworks, gRPC introduces a range of data streaming modes for real-time communication that adapts to diverse use cases.
- **Automated code generation:** gRPC simplifies development through its inherent capability for automated code generation in diverse languages like Java, C++, Python, and more. This highlights that developers do not have to manually write the code required for communication between different services. Instead, gRPC leverages protobufs to specify the service interface and message types in a language-agnostic way. After defining the service, gRPC's code generation tools automatically generate client and server code in the prescribed programming languages.
- **Bi-directional communication:** gRPC enables bi-directional communication, enabling both the client and server to independently initiate data transfers, facilitating real-time interactive applications.

4.4.2 Disadvantages of gRPC

While gRPC offers notable advantages, it is essential to recognize potential challenges, such as: (Sandoval, REST vs gRPC: Advantages and Disadvantages, 2023) (What is gRPC: Main Concepts, Pros and Cons, Use Cases, 2021)

- **Protocol requirements:** Familiarity with protobufs and HTTP/2 is required, which may not be fully supported in older browsers, potentially limiting accessibility.
- **Incomprehensible data presentation:** The transformation of data into a binary format makes gRPC's protobufs files non-human readable, in contrast to XML and JSON utilized in alternatives such as REST, presenting difficulties in debugging and inspection.

¹⁵ Protocol Buffers (protobufs) are a language-neutral, platform-neutral extensible mechanism for serializing structured data, which are used for developing programs that communicate with each other over a network or for storing data.

¹⁶ The HTTP/2 protocol is the second major version of the Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) used by the World Wide Web, and it is designed to improve the performance and efficiency of HTTP communication.

- **Maturity concerns:** Being a newer technology compared to REST, gRPC may not have the maturity observed in more established alternatives, potentially impacting widespread adoption.

To conclude, while gRPC presents innovative capabilities, its challenges in terms of complexity, browser support, non-human readable formats and learning curve emphasize the necessity for careful consideration and strategic implementation, especially in situations where these limitations may impact overall system compatibility and ease of use.

4.5 Comparison of REST, GraphQL, and gRPC

In the dynamic landscape of API development, the differences between REST, GraphQL and gRPC are crucial factors in shaping the efficiency and functionality of applications. REST embraces a stateless client-server structure, depending on HTTP methods and a resource-oriented approach. Its extensive usage and simplicity mark it as an excellent choice for traditional web applications and public APIs, emphasizing compatibility and user-friendly integration. In contrast, GraphQL stands out as a robust option, offering a declarative syntax and flexible data retrieval. End-users can explicitly specify their data requirements, eliminating the typical challenges of over-fetching or under-fetching data commonly observed in REST. It is especially tailored for scenarios with complex data structures, mobile applications and real-time functionalities leveraging the embedded support for subscriptions.

On an alternative approach, gRPC initiates a significant change focusing on high performance communication. Utilizing protobufs and supporting bi-directional streaming, gRPC outperforms REST and GraphQL in specific scenarios, particularly those requiring real-time updates and low-latency communication. Its lack of dependence on a specific language and platform makes it an attractive option for polyglot systems and microservices architectures.

Essentially, the selection between REST, GraphQL and gRPC is determined by the project's distinct needs. The simplicity and compatibility of REST stand out in straightforward applications, GraphQL shines in scenarios demanding precise data retrieval and adaptability and gRPC leads in high performance and real-time communication domains. (Sandoval, REST vs gRPC: Advantages and Disadvantages, 2023) (Ozer, 2023) (Garrett, McLarty, & Borysov, 2022) (Ahmad, 2023) (Strmecki, 2024) (Doglio, 2023) (mobileLIVE, 2023)

Table 1. Comparative Table of REST, GraphQL, and gRPC

Feature	REST	GraphQL	gRPC
Format	JSON over HTTP	JSON over HTTP	Protobufs over HTTP/2
Advantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Simplicity and ease of use - Widespread adoption - Statelessness simplifies scalability - Rich ecosystem of tools and libraries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fetches only required data, reducing over-fetching - Single endpoint for all operations - Strongly typed schema - Real-time updates with subscriptions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High performance and efficiency - Strongly typed - Supports multiple programming languages - Built-in support for streaming and real-time communication
Disadvantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Over-fetching and under-fetching of data - Multiple endpoints can become complex to manage - Limited to HTTP/1.1 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Complexity in setting up schema and resolvers - Requires understanding of GraphQL concepts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Steeper learning curve due to Protocol Buffers - Requires HTTP/2, limiting compatibility

		- Potential for complex queries impacting performance	- More complex setup and tooling
Common Use Cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Simple CRUD applications - Public APIs - Applications with less complex data needs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Complex data fetching scenarios - Client-driven applications - Real-time applications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low-latency, high-throughput applications - Microservices - Internal service communication

5. Literature Review – API Standardization

API standardization is an essential component within the domain of software development, covering a detailed set of guidelines and specifications that precisely regulate the design, development, and implementation of APIs, which serve as the pivotal for smooth communication and data exchange between various software applications. In the standardization process, a uniform framework is established, defining the structure, syntax, functionality, and behaviour of APIs.

A primary aim of API standardization is to establish consistency throughout the extensive variety of APIs, ensuring a harmonized approach that developers can universally adopt, which enables interoperability and simplified integration. Furthermore, API standardization provides a common ground for developers to build on and share their developments.

Through the definition of clear and widely accepted standards, API standardization makes a substantial contribution to the efficiency and effectiveness of software development, as a result, the developers gain advantages from a streamlined process that follows predefined norms, reducing the learning curve and speeding up the pace of innovation and the end-users experience improved compatibility among various systems.

In essence, API standardization stands out as a keystone, enabling collaboration and playing a crucial role in the overall expansion and sustainability of the software development. Understanding and implementing API standardization is the key for developers aiming to develop robust, interoperable, and futureproofed software solutions. (Xu, 2023) (Wahab, 2023) (Sanoja, 2023) (Why you should create API diagrams) (API standards) (Maas Alliance Working Group 3, 2021)

5.1 API Design

A well-designed API significantly impacts usability, evolvability, and security. Collaborative design workshops and modelling tools are essential for achieving these goals as they facilitate stakeholders to interact with and contribute to the model. Robust and scalable solutions are contingent upon effective API design, and by focusing on collaboration, alignment with business domains, and iterative refinement, the API development can meet the evolving needs of stakeholders and ensure long-term success. Also, the API design process is iterative, which entails continuous refinement informed by stakeholder feedback. Capturing aggregates and entities that emerge during design workshops is essential in developing a comprehensive API model, and its continuous validation ensures that the API remains aligned with the requirements and standards. (TRGoodwill, Writing API Design Standards, 2022) (Guimarães, 2019) (Kumar, 2024) (DuVander, A Simple API Design Walkthrough, 2019) (API design) (API Design Guide)

Once the API model reaches a stable state, a versioned API specification can be generated for technical review and validation. API definition documents, whether manually crafted or generated, undergo thorough review to ensure they adhere to standards and policies. Tools, such as OpenAPI (see 5.8), offer document linting to provide feedback on API quality, facilitating refinement and improvement. Maintaining version-aligned API specifications and following best practices for API documentation improves the usability, evolvability, and security of the API. API-first development treats API as primary interface for interacting with business capabilities, emphasizing consistency and reusability. Also, code generators and mock servers speed up the implementation process, making it easier to create prototypes quickly and iterate efficiently. Effective API design tooling is essential for facilitating collaboration, managing versioning, and ensuring adherence to standards. Meanwhile, modelling tools should facilitate document generation, source control, and validation to maintain accuracy and traceability.

Conclusively, the API design process consists of four key steps, with each step requires cooperation among stakeholders, including business leaders, developers, consumers, and partners, to guarantee the API aligns with all pertinent requirements. Collaborative engagement at each step of the API design process also helps developers avoid building unnecessary functionality. These steps are: (Geewax, 2021) (Blanchette, 2008) (Australian Government - API Design Standard, n.d.) (Rosenstock, 2019) (Best Practices in API Design) (TRGoodwill, API Design Practice, 2023)

1. **Determining the scope of the API:** In the API design process, the starting point is for all stakeholders to align on the API's business use case, which may influence the choice of architecture. For instance, a gRPC based architecture could be the best choice for an API designed to connect internal microservices, a GraphQL API may be well-suited for a service reliant on diverse data sources and a REST API could serve as a flexible option suitable for a wide range of scenarios, providing a direct approach for communication between clients and servers.
2. **Defining the API agreement through detailed specification:** After aligning all stakeholders with the API's use case, the subsequent phase is to determine the required resources, establish the formatting and structure of the data, define their relationship and the methods accessible through their associated endpoints. These decisions should be documented in an API definition, acting as a representation of an API's intended functionality that is readable by both humans and machines. API definitions adhere to API specifications, such as OpenAPI, establishing a standardized structure.
3. **Validation of assumptions through mocks and tests:** After completing the API definition, it can be utilized to generate mock servers. Mock servers provide simulated data in response to requests, validating the functionality of the API. Mocks can also be used alongside API tests, which can be executed manually, scheduled, or automated within CI/CD pipelines, as a result of identifying and addressing any issues.
4. **API documentation:** The final step is the API documentation, involving the definition of essential details about each resource, method, parameter, and path. Documentation may also include illustrations of API requests and responses, offering consumers essential insight into how a particular API addresses common business needs.

5.2 API Modelling

In the process of API development, API modelling is an essential phase, which also involves specifying the scope, functionality, and interactions of the API before proceeding with the design and implementation phases. The structured approach to API modelling ensures that the needs of both developers and end-users are met by the final API.

Beginning API design from the database might lead to the creation of the API that does not meet the needs. Conversely, API modelling as a starting point allows for consideration of how and who will use the API, and what capabilities it needs to support. Focusing on user needs over database structures, this approach leads to more effective communication and improved alignment with objectives.

The process of API modelling consists of five distinct steps, as follows:

1. **Establish the users of the API:** The first step in API modelling is identifying the participants or users who will interact with the API, which includes both developers and end-users.
2. **Identify the desired outcomes:** API modelling prioritizes the outcomes that the API will enable, rather than focusing on database structures. The identification of these desired outcomes provides insights into the functionality that the API needs to support.
3. **Map the steps required to achieve outcomes:** After identifying the desired outcomes, the next step is to map the necessary steps to achieve each outcome. This process involves breaking down the

outcomes into individual steps, each of which is accomplished using one or more endpoints from the API.

4. **Define the API Model:** As the steps are identified, the API model begins to form. Within this API model are resources and actions that represent the functionality of the API. Also, before moving into the detailed process of API design and by capturing these APIs and methods, the API requirements can be validated.
5. **Validate the API Model:** The final step in API modelling is to validate the API model against established requirements, which verifies that the API model can meet the needs by using wireframes, user stories, test cases, and other requirements. Any missing outcomes or steps should be identified before proceeding to the design and development phases.

In summary, API modelling is an essential step in the API development process, enabling the definition of the scope and functionality of the API before its design and implementation. By following the five steps outlined above, the final API can be ensured to meet the needs of both developers and end-users, leading to a more successful API implementation. (Higginbotham, 2023) (Mosyan, 2023) (API Modeling - The Process And Goals, 2020)

5.3 Documentation Standards

API documentation is essential as a connection point between developers and the complex realm of APIs, which includes a set of understandable guidelines, instructing users on the integration and utilization of an API. Complete documentation offers comprehensive details about endpoints¹⁷, methods, resources, authentication protocols, parameters, and headers. Examples of common requests and responses additionally highlight the API's functionality. The importance of API documentation is underscored by its role in ensuring the success of APIs, whether private or public. Documentation for internal use enhances collaboration across teams, reduces code duplication and expedites the onboarding process for new team members, while external documentation aids potential users in understanding and experimenting with an API, promoting higher adoption rates.

The creation of API documentation involves a multi-step approach, requiring a deep understanding of the API, empathy for its diverse audience and an iterative mindset. Moreover, certain components should be included in a comprehensive checklist, such as the API's purpose, endpoints, methods, parameters, data types and authentication mechanisms. Providing detailed instructions for common use cases, thorough testing and continuous updates are key practices for efficient API documentation. (DuVander, Beyond Static Docs: Interactive API Documentation, 2019) (API documentation) (TRGoodwill, API Documentation and Validation Rules, 2023)

5.4 Data Formats

The Data Formats initiative aims to establish a more advanced and standardized approach in managing the complex interplay of data within the continually evolving realm of modern technology, is guided by foundational principles, such as: (TRGoodwill, API Bites — Payload Conventions, 2022)

- **JSON as the default format:** JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) stands out as the primary and preferred choice, utilizing its human-readable text and adaptable structure.
- **Flexible format support:** Acknowledging various formats like XML, RSS and CSV Files, the focus remains on JSON as a baseline requirement. Adjustability is maintained to accommodate alternative media types when required.

¹⁷ An endpoint is a specific Uniform Resource Locator (URL) that represents a resource or action within an API.

- **Date-time format:** Promoting a uniform date-time format aligned with RFC3339 and ISO 8601 standards enhances compatibility for data and timestamp fields. This uniformity guarantees a smooth exchange of information.
- **Naming conventions:** Standardization in naming conventions, such as CamelCase or snake_case, for request and response fields, query parameters and resource identifiers, which enhances clarity and simplifies maintenance.
- **Resource identification standards:** Resource identifiers, whether in the form of strings or numeric values, must prioritize URL safety and immutability. Following a standardized approach for resource references, either through an "id" field (eg. "id": 12) or a concatenated resource name followed by "id" (eg. "customerId": 12), guarantees uniformity.

5.5 Versioning

API versioning is an essential aspect of API management, ensuring a structured method for implementing changes while maintaining the integrity of existing systems. It focuses on supervising and monitoring adjustments to an API, necessitating effective communication to API consumers.

Efficient API versioning is necessary for ensuring alignment between API producers and consumers throughout the API's development. A successfully implemented versioning approach minimizes the impact of breaking changes on consumers, promoting transparent communication about these modifications. These transformative adjustments (as known as breaking changes) can affect various aspects of the API, including data structures, input and output mechanisms, error handling and security protocols. Renaming properties or endpoints, altering parameter requirements, modifying data formats, and adjusting property characteristics are common scenarios warranting API versioning.

There are several approaches to API versioning, each with its unique characteristics:

- **URL versioning:** Integrating the version number in the API endpoint's URL, such as *https://example-api.com/v1/products*.
- **Query parameter versioning:** Including the version number as a query parameter in the API request, for example, *https://example-api.com/products?version=v1*.
- **Header versioning:** Passing the version number as a header in the API request, separating it from the URL structure.
- **Consumer-based versioning:** Authorizing consumers to choose and remain with a specific version based on their initial call, ensuring consistency unless explicitly modified.

The process of API versioning requires careful planning and execution, include:

1. **Version strategy:** Select an appropriate versioning strategy during the API design phase, promoting durable design patterns.
2. **Confirm necessity:** Evaluate the scope and impact of changes to determine the necessity of a new version, examining alternatives that support backward compatibility.
3. **Update documentation:** Share adjustments through updated documentation, providing insights into the reasoning, impacts, access methods, release timelines and migration instructions.
4. **Testing:** Test the new version to ensure its performance and security. This includes unit tests, integration tests, and regression tests to check for any issues.
5. **Gradual deployment:** Release the new version in phases, obtain feedback from a subset of users, address issues and then proceed to a broader release.
6. **Deprecate old version:** Monitor adoption, announce a deprecation timeline and provide assistance to users during the transition from the old to the new version.

Applying these practices will contribute to a robust and user-friendly API versioning model, fostering collaboration between producers and consumers to ensure the sustained success of the API ecosystem. (API versioning)

5.6 Authentication and Authorisation

API authentication is crucial for ensuring the security of API interactions, involving the verification of the identity of users initiating API requests and acts as a crucial foundation of API security. Diverse authentication methods are available, each with its advantages, drawbacks, and ideal use cases. The end goal persists uniformly, aiming to protect sensitive data and prevent the misuse of the API, regardless of the method used. API authentication is often utilized alongside API authorization, but they are not the same thing. API authentication, involving the validation of a user's identity, differs from API authorization, which checks whether a user has the correct permissions to perform a specific task.

One of the primary advantages of API authentication is its contribution to the protection of sensitive information. By implementing robust authentication mechanisms, API providers can build trust with users and ensure the reputation of their organization. The API-first development model, emphasizing API quality and security, ensures that API maintains high performance and scalability without becoming vulnerable for potential attackers.

In the landscape of API authentication, several methods play pivotal roles, each tailored to specific needs and security considerations:

- **HTTP Basic Authentication:** In this method, user/password pairs are dispatched via the Authorization header. Despite its simplicity, it necessitates the use of HTTPS to encrypt credentials during transmission, guaranteeing a fundamental level of security.
- **API Key Authentication:** Utilizing a unique identifier provided by API providers, this method serves as an efficient method for regulating usage and monitoring access. Every request must be accompanied by API keys, enhancing traceability and accountability. For increased security, it is recommended to integrate API key authentication alongside the implementation of HTTPS.
- **JWT (JSON Web Token) Authentication:** JWTs are digitally signed and encrypted tokens that represent user identity. Generated by the API server during user login, these tokens are included in subsequent requests. The lack of state enhances scalability since user data are not stored server-side, promoting efficient and secure communication.
- **OAuth Authentication:** Structured as a token-based mechanism, OAuth enables third-party access without compromising user login credentials. In the field of API authentication, OAuth 2.0 is recognized as a gold standard, offering flexibility and scalability. Furthermore, it facilitates comprehensive API integration while ensuring the protection of user data.

Each method operates differently, providing developers and organizations with flexibility in choosing an approach that aligns with their specific security and functionality needs.

In summary, a robust authentication and authorization framework is essential for ensuring the security, trustworthiness, and reliability of APIs. By following standards and selecting suitable authentication methods, API providers enhance the overall success and safety of their API ecosystem. (API authentication)

5.7 Error Handling

Error handling is essential for making sure users can interact smoothly and reliably with the system. In cases of API errors, it signifies potential issues either in the user's request or in the API itself, causing a temporary interruption in the flow of traffic. Errors, whether in the form of code or responses, are important for the

diagnosis and resolution of issues. They communicate failure to users, serving as the primary means of conveying information about the encountered issues. In the field of API standardization, there is an exploration of error responses and handling approaches to understand their significance and importance. The classification of errors, especially within the HTTP Status Codes format, is essential for efficient communication between clients and APIs.

HTTP Status Codes are classified into distinct ranges, each representing different aspects of communication, such as:

- The 1XX range communicates informational messages, offering insights into the current protocol state (e.g. 100 Continue - The server has received the request headers and the client should proceed to send the request body).
- The 2XX range signifies success, confirming the positive outcome of a communication attempt (e.g. 200 OK - The request has succeeded, and the server has returned the requested resource).
- The 3XX range, focusing on redirection, guides the user when the contacted point is not the correct entry point (e.g. 302 Found - The requested resource resides temporarily under a different URL).
- The 4XX range indicates client errors, revealing issues with the user's request or client status (e.g. 404 Not Found - The server cannot find the requested resource).
- The 5XX range is dedicated to server errors, highlighting failures specific to the server (e.g. 500 Internal Server Error - The server encountered an unexpected condition that prevented it from fulfilling the request).

Understanding these classified ranges simplifies the identification of the source and responsibility for encountered errors.

Characterized by three essential criteria, a good error code should, firstly, include an HTTP Status Code to determine the source of the problem. Secondly, the use of an internal reference ID supports documentation-specific notation of errors. Lastly, human-readable messages are crucial for summarizing the context, cause, and potential solutions for the encountered error.

Error handling highlights the importance of context. While a clear error code, such as *400 Bad Request* communicates the issue, it might lack sufficient context. Enriching it with additional information in the response body, like a JSON representation of the error, provides users with valuable insights into the nature of the failure. Establishing a balance between machine readability and human readability ensures that users can interpret and act upon the error effectively.

In conclusion, the effectiveness of error handling is a key component of API design. It serves the dual purpose of alerting users to failures and aiding in the troubleshooting and resolution process, making a more user-friendly, transparent, and reliable API ecosystem. (Sandoval, Best Practices for API Error Handling, 2017)

5.8 OpenAPI Overview

OpenAPI, also known as OpenAPI Specification (OAS) and formerly as Swagger, is essential in modern business environments by facilitating the clear and concise definition of APIs. In API-driven economy, it is imperative to convey API specifications repeatedly, succinctly, and deterministically to diverse stakeholders. API specification languages, such as OpenAPI, provide a standardized approach to achieving this goal. OpenAPI enables users to grasp service capabilities without immersing themselves in intricate application details by describing APIs in agnostic terms and decoupled from specific programming languages. The OAS facilitates the encoding of API specifications in either JSON or YAML formats, offering a comprehensive dictionary of commonly understood concepts within the API domain and enables a rich, yet user-friendly experience based on a simple document. This document follows stringent formatting guidelines, which

distinguish between fixed fields and patterned fields. Data types defined in the OpenAPI document are compatible with the JSON Schema Specification Draft 2020-12, including basic types such as integer, number, and string, along with optional format modifiers. Rich text formatting, supporting CommonMark markdown syntax, improves the document readability and comprehension.

The adoption and utilization of an OAS document is integral to the entire API lifecycle. Like a central highway in a transportation network, OAS is an essential channel for efficiently disseminating significant amounts of relevant information throughout the lifecycle stages, from design inception to deployment and support. This functionality becomes beneficial when considering the API lifecycle, where OAS can be seamlessly integrated at every phase. Whether it's the conceptualization of requirements, design, development, infrastructure configuration, or fostering developer experience, OAS is invaluable for streamlining processes and enhancing collaboration.

In the design phase, OAS is a conduit for translating requirements into tangible API implementations. Regardless of the starting point, creating an OAS document is essential. This API-first design approach leverages OAS to craft well-defined, versionable artifacts essential for the accuracy and efficiency of subsequent lifecycle stages. Also, the alignment between interface design and implementation is ensured by accelerating delivery while maintaining coherence.

Following the design phase, the next step involves the implementation of the API in code, development efforts are guided by OAS. Utilizing the tooling ecosystem surrounding OAS, the server-side code generation can be achieved, ensuring alignment between design specifications and implementation details. A detailed OAS document is essential for implementation success, whether adopting an API-first or code-first methodology, facilitating seamless integration, and minimizing discrepancies between design and execution.

In API management, the infrastructure configuration is essential for securing APIs and providing standardized patterns of deployment. The utilization of OAS can expedite this process by leveraging the same artifact created during the design phase while also reduce administrative overhead, ensure consistency across environments, and maximize operational efficiency and security in API gateway configurations.

The utilization of OAS as a common language for conveying API specifications accelerates the publication of relevant information, whether internally or externally. While OAS establishes the groundwork, the developer experience can be enhanced by the utilization of compatible tools to deliver interactive experiences, comprehensive documentation, and software development kits tailored to needs.

Ensuring quality and security standards requires thorough testing of the APIs. In this case, OAS showcases its worth as it provides a deterministic mechanism for executing tests. From tests to security assessments, utilizing OAS as an input enhances testing activities, ensuring alignment with API specifications, and enhancing confidence in API reliability and security.

An OpenAPI document functions as a self-contained or composite resource that defines or describes an API or its components. It adheres to the OAS and comprises essential fields such as paths, components, or webhooks. Within OpenAPI documents, path templating is a technique that allows the delineation of replaceable sections within URL paths through template expressions. These expressions relate to path parameters and must comply with specific formatting guidelines outlined by RFC3986¹⁸.

¹⁸ RFC3986, known as the Uniform Resource Identifier (URI), establishes standardized guidelines for the structure and resolution of URIs, facilitating interoperability and secure usage across the Internet.

The versioning scheme of the OAS is represented by major.minor.patch (eg. version: 3.1.0), where major and minor versions define feature sets and patch versions handle errors and clarifications within the document. Compatibility across minor versions should be maintained by tools supporting a specific version. Additionally, there may be instances where non-backwards compatible changes occasionally arise in minor versions, aiming to minimize impact while enhancing functionality.

Furthermore, the OAS is widely recognized as a description format for HTTP-based remote APIs. The OAS is maintained, evolved, and promoted by the OpenAPI Initiative (OAI), which operates under an open governance structure within the Linux Foundation, ensuring transparency and collaboration in its development, and it has gained widespread adoption for describing modern APIs. Its popularity is attributed to the extensive set of tools available for working with OpenAPI. This tools list highlights the efficacy of machine-readable API descriptions, such as OpenAPI Descriptions (OADs). As aforementioned, OADs are written as machine-readable JSON or YAML documents, with a preference for YAML's compact file size as a superset of JSON. The structure of an OAD involves an OpenAPI Object with mandatory fields, including openapi, info, and one of paths, components, or webhooks. A minimal OAD requires a JSON object with key fields such as specifying the OAS version, providing general API information, and at least one of paths, components, or webhooks.

```
1 openapi: 3.1.0
2 info:
3   title: A minimal OpenAPI Description
4   version: 0.0.1
5 paths: {} # No endpoints defined
```

Figure 5 An example of a minimal OpenAPI Description (OAD)

Conclusively, the OAS holds a crucial role in describing HTTP-like APIs, promoting standardization, and enhancing interoperability. Its machine-readable format and robust tool support are key factors in establishing it as a widely embraced industry standard. (CEN/TC 278, 2017) (OpenAPI Specification) (What is OpenAPI?)

6. Plug-and-Play Framework

The term Plug-and-Play refers to a technological capability that allows devices, systems, or components to work seamlessly together without requiring manual configuration or complex setup procedures. It is a concept rooted in simplicity, highlighting a user-friendly experience where integration and functionality are automatically enabled upon connection.

The initial purpose of the Plug-and-Play is to streamline and simplify the integration process for various technologies, promoting interoperability and ease of use. Conventionally, setting up and configuring software components required intricate knowledge, often involving technical expertise. Plug-and-Play aims to remove these barriers by providing predefined settings and automated processes, making technology more accessible to a broader range of users.

Furthermore, the Plug-and-Play ensures the seamless integration between different devices, software applications, or systems. By offering predefined settings, users can connect components effortlessly, minimizing the necessity for extensive manual configuration. This simplicity is particularly beneficial in diverse technological ecosystems where different manufacturers and developers contribute to the overall functionality, and especially in ecosystems where different actors may have different degrees of programming knowledge, or even none.

The procedure for implementing the Plug-and-Play encompasses several key steps, including: (Digital Transport and Logistics) (ATOS, 2020)

- **the definition of data requirements:** Data requirements refers to the necessary criteria for acquiring information needed to the given purpose. They provide data collection and utilization to effectively achieve the predefined objectives.
- **the development of Technology Independent Services (TIS):** Technology Independent Services (TIS) are interoperable services designed to operate across various technologies and platforms and facilitate Plug-and-Play capabilities, allowing users to effortlessly exchange data without requiring prior agreements.
- **the creation of a semantic model:** Model represents a structured representation of data, processes, or relationships within the system and aids in aligning data requirements, defining business services, and promoting interoperability. Models provide a common understanding among stakeholders participating in system development.
- **the implementation of a Service Registry:** Service Registry is a centralized system managing information regarding available services and it plays a pivotal role in enabling Plug-and-Play. The registry contains data about TIS, allowing users to explore and engage with service providers based on their business service types.

Each of the aforementioned steps is designed to contribute to the overarching goal of enabling interoperability.

The concept of the Plug-and-Play is not static, but it aligns with evolving technologies and business requirements. Continuous improvement is a crucial consideration, ensuring that Plug-and-Play infrastructure remains adaptable to new APIs, data sharing requirements, and business processes.

The key objectives of the Plug-and-Play methodology, highlighting its focus on user experience, interoperability, and the seamless integration of various stakeholders within the ecosystem, are referred below as:

- **User-Centric Philosophy:** The primary Plug-and-Play principle is a resounding user-centric philosophy, aimed to empower individual end-users in digitally sharing logistics data with potential business partners and relevant authorities. The core emphasis is on providing a platform that accommodates diverse end-users, including small and medium enterprises (SMEs), large enterprises, and authorities.
- **Ease of Accessibility:** Accessibility is a crucial aspect of the Plug-and-Play design, ensuring that the platform is effortlessly accessible by individual end-users.
- **Precision and Recall Mechanism:** Embedded within the Plug-and-Play approach is a precision and recall mechanism inspired by the efficiency of search engines. This ensures that each end-user can precisely find others offering the required logistics services (precision) and be easily discoverable by other end-users (recall).
- **Simplified Complexity:** The platform is designed to provide a seamless and straightforward user experience, abstracting the intricacies of standards and their implementation guides.
- **Openness and Interoperability:** The design principle advocates for each individual end-user to effortlessly connect to their solution of choice, fostering compliant and secure business transactions with any other end-user on the platform. This openness promotes interoperability across diverse stakeholders.
- **Single Connection Endpoint:** The peak of the Plug-and-Play approach results in a single connection, referred to as the 'endpoint' for each individual end-user. This endpoint facilitates access to the platform services, aligning effortlessly with the specific requirements of every end-user.

In essence, Plug-and-Play functionalities help technology become more user-friendly, appealing to a wider audience, including those with limited technical expertise. Its purpose is to simplify the integration process, promote accessibility, and improve efficiency, ultimately enhancing the user experience across a variety of technological applications.

Figure 6 Procedure of Plug-and-Play implementation

6.1 Design Principles for Data Sharing in Logistics

The Plug-and-Play design principle stands as the cornerstone for the development of a comprehensive logistics data sharing platform. This approach is crafted to meet the diverse needs of individual end-users, fostering a user-centric, inclusive, and easily accessible environment within the logistics sector. Below, each principle is examined for its significance and impact within the landscape of logistics data sharing:

- **Plug-and-Play Architecture:** Allows organizations to effortlessly integrate IT back-office systems, enhancing collaborative efficiency, and supports user registration and ontology development, establishing a robust foundation for efficient data sharing.
- **Predefined Settings for Seamless Integration:** Represents a progression towards Plug-and-Play providing predefined specifications for document data sets and visibility events, enabling organizations the capability to communicate and integrate data effectively, simplifying complexities connected with data sharing.

- **Federation of Platforms:** Establishes an open and neutral environment, fostering interoperability across diverse platforms, and permits users the ability to exchange data without prior agreements, guaranteeing fairness and fostering collaboration throughout the logistics ecosystem.
- **Technology Independent Services (TIS):** TIS play a central role in achieving Plug-and-Play and utilize the Service Registry for configuration, ensuring the standardization of data sharing and enhancing interoperability.
- **Business Choreography Deployment:** Encompasses extensive deployment of business choreography through the Service Registry, highlighting Plug-and-Play implementation, streamlining logistics operations, and ensuring uniformity in data sharing practices.
- **Threat Mitigation:** Deals with risks related to intermediation and disintermediation, establishing a secure data-sharing environment, and standardizes TIS and Plug-and-Play functionalities, providing protection against potential threats and fostering trust within the logistics ecosystem.
- **Guidelines and Use Cases:** Improves the utility of the semantic model, providing guidance for integration into supply and logistics chains, and simplifies data sharing between enterprises (B2B) and compliance with authority data requirements (B2A), ensuring standardized and regulated data-sharing practices.

In contemporary logistics ecosystem, Logistics Service Providers (LSPs) are used for ensuring seamless data exchange and operational integration. However, traditional approaches often involve LSPs developing their own proprietary interfaces and mappings to comply with multiple standards, which can be costly and challenging for smaller companies with limited IT resources.

The concept of standardized profiles, as advocated by initiatives like FEDeRATED, helps address these issues effectively. These standardized profiles offer a unified framework that simplifies integration efforts for SMEs, allowing them to align with industry standards without extensive customization.

SMEs in the EU face barriers such as limited financial resources and IT expertise, making the adoption of proprietary LSP interfaces impractical. Standardized profiles provide SMEs with accessible tools to streamline integration processes, ensuring compliance with regulatory requirements and enhancing interoperability across the logistics network.

To accommodate diverse organizational needs, localization of APIs within a Plug-and-Play framework is essential. A node within the architecture can act as an API gateway, configuring APIs to align with organizational standards and operational requirements. This localization strategy supports adaptability and scalability, enabling organizations to customize integration solutions without needing extensive development resources.

In conclusion, the Plug-and-Play design principle represents a pivotal step towards creating a more inclusive, user-friendly, and interoperable logistics data sharing environment.

6.2 Applying Plug-and-Play Framework

The findings from FEDeRATED and FENIX provide significant insights that have shaped KEYSTONE's approach. After thoroughly studying the work conducted in the context of the said DTLF's supporting projects, several key outtakes can be taken, in regard to Plug-and-Play and its implementation, which will be utilised in the context of the project. FENIX and FEDeRATED undertook the challenge of implementing Plug-and-Play capabilities within their respective architectures, each with distinct approaches and emphases (The Digital Transport and Logistics Forum Second Mandate (DTLF II) - Subgroup 2: corridor information systems).

FENIX prioritized the establishment of a decentralized ecosystem, akin to a federation, wherein participants could seamlessly share data and access services. The project focused on developing a European Federated Network of Information exchange in Logistics, to enable seamless data sharing for Business-to-Business (B2B) and Business-to-Administration (B2A) exchanges, outlining the foundational needs for the establishment of such a federated network, as well as a system architecture, its components, interfaces and standards to guide the development. This decentralization was crucial for ensuring scalability and accommodating a diverse array of stakeholders, upon which insight the KEYSTONE aims to build. Moreover, FENIX underscored the significance of open standards to facilitate interoperability and streamline integration processes. By leveraging widely adopted standards, FENIX aimed to foster economies of scale and network effects, thereby simplifying connectivity and collaboration across the ecosystem (Maria Pia Fanti, 2020).

In contrast, FEDeRATED placed a strong emphasis on semantic integration, employing standards such as OWL, RDF, and SHACL to specify machine-readable data. This project aimed to establish a validated master plan of EU federated network of platforms and develop a prototype data-sharing environment for business and public sector use. Semantic interoperability formed the cornerstone of Plug-and-Play implementation in FEDeRATED, enabling stakeholders to exchange information digitally with precision and clarity. The project also developed a multimodal ontology, aligning existing ontologies and standards to represent concepts and properties pertinent to logistics and supply chain management. This meticulous ontology development ensured consistency and interoperability across disparate domains, laying a robust foundation for seamless integration (Masterplan - Technical Specifications - High Level Architecture, 2023).

First and foremost, FENIX and FEDeRATED provided valuable insights into the practical implementation of Plug-and-Play principles. They offered more than theoretical insights; they provided tangible examples of how Plug-and-Play principles can be implemented in real-world scenarios. By studying the practical outcomes of these projects, such as their architectures, service registries, semantic models, KEYSTONE was able to move beyond abstract principles and understand the technical and operational aspects of Plug-and-Play implementation. These tangible results informed the development of the API Reference Model, allowing KEYSTONE to design a framework that is not only conceptually sound but also practical and applicable to the challenges identified in its use cases.

Both FENIX and FEDeRATED recognized the pivotal role of Service Registries and Indexes in facilitating discoverability, data sharing, and access control within the federated network. The role of Service Registries and Indexes were essential components for federated architectures, as they served as vital infrastructure, enabling participants to locate and access relevant services and data sources efficiently. KEYSTONE can develop and deploy similar infrastructure components to streamline the identification and utilization of services and data sources within federated environments. KEYSTONE drew inspiration from the concept of Service Registries and Indexes, as emphasised in FENIX and FEDeRATED, to address discoverability and efficient access to data sources and services. While these components were not directly integrated into the UML model presented in 8 of this document, they influenced the structured approach to defining the necessary API interactions and ensuring alignment with the requirements of the KEYSTONE use cases, as defined in the context of Task 1.4 in the project, and as outlined briefly in section 7.2.

Furthermore, they demonstrated different approaches to Plug-and-Play implementation, but both projects highlighted the importance of semantic interoperability, open standards, decentralization, and trust and security for enabling seamless integration and collaboration within federated networks. Also, those two projects highlighted certain gaps that exist in the field. One key gap was the lack of universally adopted standards, which, despite both projects emphasizing interoperability, occasionally hindered seamless integration. Another challenge was ensuring consistent data interpretation across diverse systems, highlighting the need for robust semantic alignment. Furthermore, as the number of participants increased, the importance of scalability became evident to maintain performance and effectively manage the growing

complexity of interactions. These insights and lessons can be valuable for future projects and especially for KEYSTONE, which aims to implement Plug-and-Play capabilities. KEYSTONE attempts to address such gaps by designing a scalable API Reference Model that can adapt to growing participant numbers, while staying aligned with the Plug and Play principles, and which will lead to an API standard that will standardise data exchanges between 3rd party applications and the app under development in WP3.

The emphasis on open standards for interoperability, observed in both projects, highlights the importance of adopting widely accepted protocols and specifications. KEYSTONE can leverage existing standards to ensure compatibility and ease of integration across heterogeneous systems and domains. By defining consistent protocols and interaction patterns, the API standard ensures uniformity in data exchange, eliminating ambiguities and fostering seamless integration across systems. For data producers, the API standard, that will derive from the API reference model, will provide a clear framework for defining and implementing standardised APIs, ensuring their data is structured and shared in a consistent and interoperable manner, while for the data consumers (e.g. law enforcement authorities) it will enable easy comprehension of the aforementioned standardised APIs, ensuring they can accurately interpret and utilise the data provided, eliminating confusion or mismatches in data formats or expectations. This approach ensures that both ends of the data exchange process are aligned.

In addition, the focus on semantic interoperability, as exemplified by FEDeRATED, underscores the significance of standardized data representation and exchange mechanisms. By developing a comprehensive ontology aligned with relevant industry standards, KEYSTONE can facilitate precise and unambiguous communication between disparate stakeholders, enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of data sharing within federated networks. This inspired KEYSTONE to build upon this and define data structures and attributes by consulting extensively with logistics companies within the consortium and external entities, such as MOVEHUB and EUCARIS, in close collaboration with Task 2.2 leader and identifying all those necessary elements required for the API Reference Model at this stage, and the API Standard in the future. These consultations ensured that the model reflects practical needs and will be further enriched and refined in the API Standard to support consistent and effective data exchange across systems for the pilots' purposes in WP4.

Moreover, the decentralization approach embraced by FENIX, wherein participants act as decentralized nodes within a federation, offers insights into scalable and resilient architectures for federated systems. Its primary focus was on decentralization, enabling interoperability through connectors and service registries while preserving data sovereignty and ownership. KEYSTONE explored FENIX's approach to empower diverse stakeholders while promoting flexibility and adaptability in network configurations. KEYSTONE emphasizes creating a standardized framework that simplifies integration rather than federating existing platforms. In particular, KEYSTONE, with the usage of the standardised API framework aims to facilitate seamless communication between data producers and consumers. This entails creating an API standard derived from the API Reference Model outlined in this deliverable, which will serve as the basis for linking data producers with data consumers, while maintaining its scalability. By adhering to this standardized API framework, KEYSTONE can enable platform-to-platform communication, fostering interoperability and facilitating the exchange of data between different systems, while data can stay in essence at the source. FENIX emphasised decentralization and federation of existing platforms, while KEYSTONE prioritises creating a new, standardized API framework to unify data exchange. While FENIX focuses on enabling interoperability within a federated network, KEYSTONE ensures uniformity and scalability with a standardised framework. This approach will contribute to the project's goal of promoting a platform-to-platform approach within the DTLF ecosystem.

Furthermore, FEDeRATED emphasized the importance of Identification, Authentication, and Authorization (IAA) mechanisms for ensuring trust and security in data exchange. Organizational trust and inter-

organizational trust formed the bedrock of IAA, supported by measures such as cyber security and distributed identity solutions. This emphasis on trust and security, particularly in data exchange processes, as demonstrated by both projects, highlights the critical importance of robust Identification, Authentication, and Authorization (IAA) mechanisms. Inspired by FEDeRATED's emphasis on IAA mechanisms, KEYSTONE aims to research into incorporating robust authentication protocols, such as eID and eIDAS. KEYSTONE can prioritize the implementation of secure and verifiable identity solutions, coupled with stringent access control measures, to instill trust and confidence in data sharing activities across federated networks. For this aspect, Task 2.2 focuses on integrating eID authentication into API architecture for secure data access, while exploring cross-data space authentication mechanisms in line with IDSA objectives. Deliverable 2.2 showcases real-world use-cases involving drivers, vehicles, and infrastructure, illustrating seamless interoperability through standardized APIs. It documents eID authentication procedures and best practices, serving as a valuable guide for stakeholders implementing similar mechanisms in federated networks.

In conclusion, building on the aforementioned concepts, KEYSTONE introduces the API Reference Model as the blueprint for creating the API Standard, which addresses a key missing element: a unified, technology-agnostic API framework. Unlike FEDeRATED, which focuses on the configuration of existing systems, and FENIX, which emphasizes semantic integration and decentralized connectors, KEYSTONE adopts a more unified approach by developing a standardized API framework that is both technology-agnostic and modular. This ensures minimal complexity for stakeholders while providing a common structure for interaction. API Standard will be designed to allow stakeholders to integrate standardized APIs into their systems regardless of the underlying legacy systems, or technologies in use. This approach creates a universal API "glossary" for all stakeholders to follow and adopt, aligned with the Plug-and-Play principles, and fostering seamless data exchange and interoperability. That way each stakeholder's system does not require configurations or radical changes of any kind and may, through the definition of APIs in accordance with the standard, define their own APIs with minimal development effort in order to achieve connection with platforms, while they retain their autonomy, ensuring safe, decentralized control over their data and operations.

The KEYSTONE web app, which will be developed in WP3, will act as a demonstrator and end user of the API Standard, validating its real-world applicability. By integrating the API Standard and enabling communication between different federated platforms, KEYSTONE will complete the concept of Plug-and-Play and its principles as mentioned in Section 6.1. Importantly, the API Standard and its implementation as a Python library in Task 2.3 will not be limited to the scope of the KEYSTONE project; they are designed for broader applicability, enabling platform-to-platform communication beyond the project's timeline. By adhering to the API Standard, stakeholders can ensure efficient and consistent data exchange across diverse platforms. The web app will leverage the standardized APIs provided by the Python library to demonstrate the ease of achieving interoperability and scalability in logistics operations.

Furthermore, the API Reference Model, API Standard, and consequently the Python library will be developed as a unified framework with a strong emphasis on modularity and openness. This design approach ensures ease of future extensions, seamless integrations with additional platforms, and broader adoption by stakeholders, while also accommodating a wider range of real-world use cases. By establishing a robust foundation for interoperability and Plug-and-Play functionality, KEYSTONE's contributions will remain impactful even beyond the project, supporting a connected, efficient, and scalable logistics ecosystem.

Specifically, the API Reference Model outlined and the standardization findings from Task 2.3 that will be produced later on will serve as guidelines for implementing standardized API endpoints within the web app architecture. By aligning with these standards, the web app can seamlessly communicate with various data sources and platforms, promoting interoperability and ease of integration.

Overall, the investigation into Plug-and-Play frameworks conducted in WP2 provides insights into how interoperability and scalability can be achieved within the KEYSTONE ecosystem. By adopting Plug-and-Play principles, the API Standard and consequently the web app can be designed to easily integrate with existing platforms and data sources during and beyond the project's timeline, thus having increased potential for being utilised and connected with more platforms and already existing applications, as well as others that may come in the future, facilitating smooth data exchange and communication between different stakeholders. Lastly, KEYSTONE can create a robust and interoperable enforcement solution that meets the needs of various stakeholders and ensures seamless data exchange and communication across the ecosystem.

6.3 Association with OpenAPI

According to Section 5.8, OpenAPI stands as a valuable specification for API development, providing a standardized method for defining REST APIs, and which facilitates clear communication between diverse systems and services. Through its standardization, developers can seamlessly understand and integrate with APIs, promoting a more straightforward and consistent method of data sharing. While OpenAPI primarily focuses on API documentation, its commitment to industry standards contributes to the overarching goal of creating an environment suitable for Plug-and-Play interactions across an ecosystem of diverse applications and services.

Traditionally, APIs have often employed a coupled communication model, where the caller initiates a request and waits for a synchronous response, halting the process until a result is returned. This approach ensures immediate feedback, but can introduce latency and hinder scalability, particularly in dynamic environments.

Moving beyond traditional coupled communication, asynchronous communication models are gaining prominence. Asynchronous APIs decouple interactions between services, allowing the caller to continue operations while awaiting responses asynchronously. This approach enhances system agility and responsiveness, important for applications requiring real-time data processing and scalability. Implementing asynchronous APIs should thus be a priority in environments demanding flexibility and rapid response times.

In contemporary integration landscapes, the concept of an API cloud has become a fundamental architectural paradigm. The API cloud encompasses a diverse ecosystem of APIs, each serving distinct functionalities and accommodating varying endpoints. This diversity is particularly pertinent in logistics, where the ability to support multiple API configurations enhances operational agility and resilience.

Within logistics operations, the variety of endpoints within the API cloud highlights the need for a robust Plug-and-Play approach. Different logistics providers and systems necessitate flexible API integrations that can adapt to unique operational requirements seamlessly.

In summary, OpenAPI is essential in standardizing and documenting APIs, which can contribute to the development of a more interoperable and user-friendly environment. Moreover, a Plug-and-Play architecture enables organizations to promote collaboration and streamline logistics operations by improving interoperability across different platforms and technologies.

7. Use Cases: Findings from WP1

7.1 WP1 Key Findings

As the respective deliverables of WP1 highlight and as the D1.4: Digital ecosystem framework (Fabrizio Borgogna, 2024), the final output of task T1.4, summarises, there is a unanimous acknowledgment of the pivotal role played by data and technology in enhancing compliance checks among almost all respondents of the survey (T1.1: takeholders' Definition and Needs), the interviews and focus groups that were consulted (T1.2: State of the Art and Requirements). However, logistic operators identified several barriers, including complex legislation, geopolitical factors such as Brexit, and concerns over confidentiality and competition. In addition, T1.3: Study of Existing Digital Platforms examined the primary data exchange platforms used in the logistics sector and, combined with insights from previous tasks, revealed significant gaps impeding the development of a digital logistics ecosystem. The review highlighted disparities in connectivity between platforms used by logistic operators and those used by enforcement authorities. Key gaps include digitalization challenges such as lack of robust security measures, interoperability issues, and the persistence of paper-based document sharing. Accessibility issues stem from non-acceptance of electronic documents, competition among stakeholders, and language barriers, while regulatory gaps involve the absence of mandatory digital platform use and harmonized laws across Member States. Addressing these gaps through interoperability, standardization, regulatory harmonization, and stakeholder collaboration is essential for realizing an efficient, fully digital logistics ecosystem that benefits all stakeholders by improving data exchange, speeding up processes, reducing costs, and increasing overall efficiency.

Despite the recognition of the importance of data sharing, challenges persist. While approximately 60% of freight terminals and logistic operators engage in data sharing with enforcement authorities, barriers such as the lack of suitable tools for terminals and confidentiality concerns for operators hinder broader participation.

The absence of a unified platform for data exchange was evident, with stakeholders relying on various commercial and proprietary solutions. Major platforms mentioned included those by SAP, IBM, and projects by the Open Logistics Foundation. Additionally, limited interaction was observed between stakeholders and existing EU platforms, necessitating improved integration and accessibility.

Regulatory disparities across European nations regarding the acceptance of digital documents remain a significant challenge, contributing to uncertainties for operators. Although the introduction of eFTI is viewed positively, standardization across Europe is not yet achieved. Interoperability issues among different e-CMR solutions further complicate matters.

To address these challenges, stakeholders are encouraged to collaborate on the development of a unified digital platform for streamlined data exchange, promoting interoperability and simplification. Efforts should also focus on enhancing integration with existing EU platforms to improve accessibility and usability.

Regulatory harmonization is paramount, requiring concerted efforts to align regulations across European countries to facilitate standardization and streamline processes. Furthermore, the promotion of federated data sharing platforms, such as Data Mobility Spaces, can address concerns surrounding data security and control.

In conclusion, addressing technological barriers, promoting collaboration among stakeholders, and advocating for regulatory harmonization are essential steps towards improving cross-border logistics controls. By implementing these recommendations, stakeholders can work towards establishing a more efficient and transparent cross-border logistics ecosystem.

7.2 Overview of Use Cases

Data exchange, interoperability, authority interaction, and regulatory compliance are essential for efficient logistics operations. While the requirements of stakeholders identified in WP1 are important, addressing these operational pillars ensures that the use cases are not only aligned with stakeholders' needs but are also viable within the regulatory and operational frameworks. This is why it is crucial to further explore the use cases of the KEYSTONE project, as defined in the context of T1.4 and its end result, the Deliverable 1.4.

This section provides an overview of the identified use cases, as they were described in D1.4, Digital Ecosystem Framework, composed by Gruber Logistics, for the project, focusing on transportation scenarios and the involvement of various stakeholders, including public and private entities, regulatory authorities, and administrative bodies. The aim is to outline the key characteristics, requirements, and functionalities of each use case to facilitate the formulation of an appropriate API Reference Model.

The information presented regarding the use cases is a work in progress. WP4 officially commenced its tasks after the submission of Deliverable D2.1 (M14), and was not active during the compilation of Deliverable D1.4. However, significant preparatory work was carried out prior to WP4's official start, to identify involved stakeholders, define transport modes and border crossing points, elaborate the legs of each journey, and determine the necessary data types for law enforcement and port operations in specific scenarios, and thus the requirements the API reference model needed to take into account, in order to serve as a basis for the future API Standard. As such, the details provided are subject to further refinement and validation as the project progresses.

Use Case 1: Road transport digital ecosystem

This use case pertains to a monomodal transportation scenario predominantly utilizing road transport for the shipment of goods. The use case will comply with an extra EU management shipment with eCMR sharing. During the pilot, a container will be loaded from a manufacturing company and transported toward a port, where a shift to maritime transport will occur. KEYSTONE aims to support port authorities in managing traffic and access of trucks headed toward the gate of the port. To this regard, the next activities (see WP4) will focus on the following aspects:

- **Stakeholders:** Three important stakeholders will be involved:
 - A port authority. It will be external to the KEYSTONE consortium and will be crucial for testing the KEYSTONE solution.
 - A logistic operator. GRUBER Logistics, partner of KEYSTONE, will actively participate to the piloting activities.
 - A group of truck drivers. GRUBER Logistics will be responsible of identifying, informing and managing a group of truck drivers. These drivers might be employees of GRUBER Logistics or provided from external suppliers. In general, big logistic operators (GRUBER Logistics can be considered a big company) rely on both options for ensuring transportation services worldwide.
- **Data:** In KEYSTONE, private stakeholders are expected to share data with public authorities. So, in this pilot, the logistic operator (GRUBER Logistic) and truck drivers will share data by APIs. For the purposes of this pilot, the expected data types to be provided to authorities are e-CMR for enabling the exchange of ITU information (ITU being the container documentation), driver's data, and estimated time of arrival of the truck. These data will be accessed from the KEYSTONE web-app (under development in WP3) for demonstrating the benefits of a digital ecosystem highlighting the support to port authorities. On the other hand, public authorities are not expected to share data (as it is sensitive information and not public) with KEYSTONE. Nevertheless, to demonstrate the benefits

provided from the project, KEYSTONE will generate “mock-up data” that are supposed to be owned and/or used from authorities (e.g., driver license, tachograph data, etc.).

- Duration: The piloting activity will last at least three months. In this time period specific KPIs (T5.1) will be monitored and measured for evaluating the impact on logistic operations.
- Timing: It is foreseen that the necessary data are to be available to the port authority during each leg of the truck journey, meaning from planning phase until its arrival at the port.

Use Case 2: Intermodal digital ecosystem

This use case refers to a multimodal transportation scenario, involving the movement of goods utilizing multiple modes of transport, specifically rail and road. The journey begins with an intermodal rail shipment originating from a port, and transitioning to an inland terminal (based in Novara, Italy, and, owned from the CIM partner). Subsequently, the last-mile transportation operation is conducted via road, with enforcement authorities overseeing the process. KEYSTONE aims to support road enforcers in conducting checks and inspections for ensuring safety on the roads. To this regard, the next activities (see WP4) will focus on the following aspects:

- Stakeholders: Three important stakeholders will be involved:
 - A road enforcer. It will be external to the KEYSTONE consortium and will be crucial for testing the KEYSTONE solution. As the pilot will be in Italy, the enforcer will be likely the Italian Highway Patrol.
 - A logistic operator: GRUBER Logistics, partner of KEYSTONE, will actively participate to the piloting activities.
 - A group of truck drivers. GRUBER Logistics will be responsible of identifying, informing and managing a group of truck drivers. These drivers might be employees of GRUBER Logistics or provided from external suppliers. In general, big logistic operators (GRUBER Logistics can be considered a big company) rely on both options for ensuring transportation services worldwide.
 - A freight village. CIM (Centro Interportuale Merci), partner of KEYSTONE, will actively participate to the piloting activities.
- Data: In KEYSTONE, private stakeholders are expected to share data with public authorities. So, in this pilot, the logistic operator (GRUBER Logistic), truck drivers and the freight village (CIM – Centro Interportuale Merci) will share data by APIs. Data will entail container documentation, train information, estimated time of arrival of each mode, as well as authorized driver’s data, truck data and updated information regarding time of arrival to the destination. These data will be accessed from the KEYSTONE web-app for demonstrating the benefits of a digital ecosystem highlighting the support to road enforcers. On the other hand, public authorities are not expected to share data (as it is sensitive information and not public) with KEYSTONE. Nevertheless, to demonstrate the benefits provided from the project, KEYSTONE will generate “mock-up data” that are supposed to be owned and/or used from authorities (e.g., driver license, tachograph data, etc.).
- Duration: The piloting activity will last at least three months. In this time period specific KPIs (T5.1) will be monitored and measured for evaluating the impact on logistic operations.
- Timing: Compliance check during transit. Data will be provided to the road enforcers upon request during the road transit of freight, after having an overview of operations via the web app and identifying specific trucks for inspection.

Both use cases include private entities along with regulatory bodies like enforcement . For both use cases, KEYSTONE is going to fulfill the following requirements:

- **Data Exchange.** Both use cases require seamless and real-time data exchange among stakeholders. This involves sharing information such as transport identifiers, vehicle and driver data, estimated time of arrival (ETA), cargo details, etc.
- **Interoperability.** The IT systems of stakeholders involved in the pilots must be interoperable with the KEYSTONE platform, enabling seamless integration and data flow. This requires standardized APIs and protocols to facilitate communication across diverse systems and stakeholders.
- **Regulatory Compliance.** Compliance with regulatory requirements and documentation standards is essential in both use cases, particularly concerning cargo manifests, and, transport permits. The KEYSTONE platform must support these compliance measures to ensure more efficient operations.
- **Authority Interaction.** Interaction with regulatory and administrative authorities (e.g., port authorities) is a critical aspect of both scenarios. The KEYSTONE platform should facilitate efficient communication and data sharing with these authorities to streamline processes and minimize delays.

The identified use cases provide valuable insights into the complexity of regulatory compliance, integration and interoperability challenges that exist and are needed to be foreseen, as well as the necessity of real-time tracking and visibility within transportation and logistics. To address regulatory requirements across road and rail transport modes, standardized documentation APIs are essential for generating bills of lading and customs declarations, supported by integration with regulatory databases for compliance checks. Permission management APIs streamline the handling of licenses and permissions, ensuring seamless cross-border and multimodal operations. Intermodal coordination APIs facilitate data exchange between stakeholders, enhancing interoperability across diverse transportation management systems. Real-time tracking APIs provide stakeholders with visibility into shipment locations, status updates, and estimated time of arrival (ETA) calculations, supported by data analytics APIs that optimize routes and improve fleet management efficiency. Customer notification APIs ensure timely updates on shipment status changes, delays, and other critical events, enhancing operational transparency and efficiency throughout the logistics journey.

By understanding the key characteristics and stakeholder interactions in each scenario, WP2 can formulate an API Reference Model that effectively addresses the needs of the KEYSTONE project. This model will serve as a foundation for developing interoperable APIs and protocols, enabling seamless integration with existing IT systems and stakeholders involved in transportation operations.

As the demonstration scenarios will be further elaborated and refined in the context of WP4, so will the API standard that will be build based on the API reference model.

8. API Reference Model

In today's logistic sector, seamless communication and interoperability among various systems are paramount. Organizations and authorities using different and frequently incompatible systems cause significant challenges to the industry. For instance, a transport operator might use one type of software to manage their logistics, while an authority might use an entirely different system or manual approach to oversee compliance, resulting in difficulties and leading to a fragmented environment where data exchange is complicated and vulnerable to errors. Moreover, the lack of standardization can lead to delays, increase cost and operational inefficiencies. The increasing complexity of logistic operations, including various modes such as rail, road, and maritime, makes the integration of different systems even more complicated. Each mode may have its own protocols and data formats, which are not easily compatible with others. Considering this fragmentation, there's a need for a robust, scalable framework that can enable standardized communication and ensure compatibility among all stakeholders, regardless of their systems. Without such a framework, managing complex logistics operations becomes a challenging task, often leading to bottlenecks and decreased operational efficiency.

The API Reference Model is the foundational framework that guides the design and implementation of the API Standard, ensuring seamless communication across platforms. It provides the architectural blueprint for the creation of the API Standard, which will be defined in an OpenAPI Specification (OAS), hosted online, and readily available for any user who wishes to adopt the standard for their own system. By utilizing the OAS and its guidelines, users will be able to implement their own standardized APIs based on their specific needs. The API Standard, alongside the API Reference Model under the same umbrella of novelty and standardization, will offer a solution to the long-standing challenges of interoperability, data fragmentation, and inefficient document exchange within the logistics sector, bridging the gap between theoretical concepts and actionable implementation, and setting a new standard for interoperability in the transport and logistics sector. The API Standard will be fully specified in Deliverable 2.3 - 1st version of the standard (due in month M25 of the project, May 2025) and Deliverable 2.4 - 2nd and final version of it (due in month M30, November 2025), which will outline its technical specifications, data models, and validation rules. These specifications will be implemented in the Python library, which will be integrated into the Keystone Web App in WP3 for demonstrating and validating the concept of standardization. Both the aforementioned deliverables, the two versions of the standard will entail the OAS and the Python Library. The OAS will provide detailed schemas for endpoints, data model, request/response structures and comprehensive guidelines, while the Python library in GitHub will provide pre-built modules and functions for data exchange and ready-to-use code templates to simplify API definition and integration for developers.

The API Standard will be designed to meet the needs of all stakeholders involved in logistics operations, including organizations and enforcement authorities. By providing a standardized approach to data exchange, it enables interoperability and facilitates the smooth flow of information between different systems, paving the way for more efficient logistics operations.

The API Standard will be further refined and detailed in Deliverable 2.3, which will provide the finalized specifications and guidelines for its implementation. It will then be extended in Deliverable 2.4, where it will be adapted and enhanced based on the feedback and requirements from the pilot implementations in WP4. This ensures that the API Standard evolves to meet the practical needs of the stakeholders, and is scalable to support a broader range of logistics operations.

The API Reference Model forms the basis for smooth communication and compatibility in the logistic sector. Based on a strong set of technical specifications and interoperability considerations, this model is designed to ensure compatibility across diverse systems and facilitate efficient data exchange between organizations and enforcement authorities. It is a comprehensive framework that outlines the standards and protocols for data exchange. By using the API Reference Model, different systems within the logistic sector can communicate seamlessly, ensuring that data is transferred accurately and efficiently. This model acts as a common language that bridges diverse systems, making sure they work together without issues.

At its core, REST principles are integrated into the API Reference Model, enabling stateless communication and scalability. Data exchanged through the API is formatted using JSON, ensuring simplicity and readability. Additionally, communication between clients and servers is secured using the HTTPS, ensuring the confidentiality and integrity of data. By providing a clear guide to its capabilities and endpoints, the API Reference Model enables seamless integration and interoperability across the logistic ecosystem.

8.1 Methodology

The methodology employed in the creation of the API Reference Model is designed to ensure its efficient and systematic development. A structured approach is pursued to attain clarity, consistency, and effectiveness in the development process, ultimately leading to the successful realization of project objectives.

The methodology involves a comprehensive analysis of the requirements and the definition of use cases, as outlined in sections 7.1 and 7.2, acting as a key component essential for understanding the functional and non-functional requirements of the system and identifying the key use cases that the API Reference Model must support. Through the Task 1.4, the core functionalities and interactions required for seamless data exchange between organizations and authorities are identified, resulting in a standardized approach to document sharing and compliance verification. This approach allows for the efficient transmission of essential information, such as driver and vehicle details, transport operation type, etc., ensuring that all stakeholders have access to accurate and up-to-date data.

Once the requirements are established, the emphasis shifts to designing the architecture and structure of the API Reference Model. This involves the creation of UML diagrams, such as class diagrams and sequence diagrams, in order to visualize the components, relationships, and interactions within the system. (Rossi, 2016)

Adherence to best practices and design principles ensures that the API architecture achieves scalability, modularity, and adaptability to future enhancements. Additionally, the usage of documentation secures the usability and maintainability of the API Reference Model.

Finally, the methodology entails deploying the API Reference Model into use cases, with deployment strategies carefully planned to facilitate a seamless transition to the operational phase.

8.2 Technical Specifications and Interoperability Considerations

The API Reference Model is supported by a robust set of technical specifications and interoperability considerations to ensure effective communication and compatibility across diverse systems. Table 2 presents the specifications that steer the design of the model, enhancing standardized data exchange and efficient integration between organizations and authorities.

Table 2. Technical Specifications

Specification	Description
REST Architecture	The API follows the principles of REST, enabling stateless communication.
JSON Data Format	Data exchanged through the API is formatted using JSON for simplicity and readability.
HTTPS Protocol	Communication between clients and servers is secured using the HTTPS to ensure data confidentiality and integrity.

The key requirements of the API Reference Model and consequently the API Standard were selected based on their ability to address the specific challenges within the project and the defined use cases. These challenges include ensuring seamless data exchange across diverse stakeholders, such as logistics providers, regulatory authorities, and enforcement agencies that conduct the compliance checks. For instance, traditional logistics operations and compliance checks often relied on physical documents, causing delays, errors, and inefficiencies in data handling and verification. Furthermore, diverse stakeholders, such as logistics providers, regulatory authorities, and enforcement agencies, often operated isolated systems, making seamless data exchange and interoperability difficult. In addition, another challenge is that port authorities need more streamlined operations, so they may handle increasing freight volumes and have accurate information regarding freight and times of arrival beforehand, to avoid bottlenecks and process loading and unloading of containers more efficiently. The API reference model and standard aim to address those challenges and enable them to achieve higher operational efficiency.

Regarding the decision to use REST architecture ensures simplicity, scalability, and stateless communication, which are essential for handling the dynamic and distributed nature of logistics operations. JSON was chosen for data format due to its lightweight structure, enabling easy integration and readability across systems. The use of HTTPS guarantees secure communication, addressing the critical need for data confidentiality and integrity in sensitive logistics operations. That way sensitive data exchanged during operations will have sufficient security measure, reducing risks of breaches and ensure trust between stakeholders and towards the web app.

Establishing the foundation for the design of the API Reference Model, these specifications ensure alignment with industry standards and best practices in interoperability. In Task 2.3, the API Standard will leverage the API Reference Model to document its interface, equipping users with a comprehensive overview of its functionalities and endpoints.

Figure 7 API Reference Model

The UML diagram (see Figure 7) illustrates the API Reference Model and its structure and relationships of the API components, including endpoints, requests, and responses. The emphasis on scalability, simplicity, and performance makes this architecture perfect for distributed systems in logistic sector, and it emphasizes interoperability considerations to ensure compatibility with the systems used by organizations and authorities.

The APIs developed under this model adhere to the CRUD (Create, Read, Update, Delete) principles, ensuring consistency, simplicity, and alignment with current known business cases in the logistics sector.

Similarly, the data model follows these principles to support effective data manipulation. This approach ensures that the API operations address the core requirements for seamless communication and data exchange. Additionally, the comprehensive APIs and the finalized data model will be fully detailed in Deliverable 2.3, while considering that related deliverables—focusing on the comprehensive vision of data exchange in the logistics sector—will remain incomplete until this deliverable is completed. Deliverable 2.4 will subsequently extend both the data model and the APIs to meet the specific needs of the pilot implementations and their outputs.

Furthermore, below is a reference point for the classes, their descriptions, attributes, and methods in the API Reference Model. It highlights the essential components and functionalities of the API, providing insights into its structure and purpose. Through these class descriptions and attributes, the API can be effortlessly integrated and deployed within the systems, contributing to the smooth flow of data and information.

The **API** is the central interface of the API Reference Model responsible for coordinating communication between organizations and authorities for data exchange in the logistics sector. It includes attributes such as **organizationEndpoint**, which represents the endpoint for organization-related requests, and **authorityEndpoint**, which represents the endpoint for authority-related requests. The methods associated with the API are **receiveDocuments()**, **provideDocuments()**, **receiveDocumentsInAdvance()**, **provideDocumentsInAdvance()**, **updateDocuments()**, and **deleteDocuments()**.

The **organizationEndpoint** is an endpoint dedicated to handling organization-related requests within the API Reference Model. It facilitates organizations in receiving and providing documents to and from the API. This endpoint has attributes including **id**, an identifier for the organization endpoint, and **apiKey**, an API key used for authentication and access control. The methods for this endpoint are **receiveDocuments()**, **provideDocuments()**, **provideDocumentsInAdvance()**, **updateDocuments()**, and **deleteDocuments()**.

The **authorityEndpoint** is designed for handling authority-related requests within the API Reference Model, facilitating authorities in receiving documents from operators through the API. Its attributes include **id**, an identifier for the authority endpoint, and **apiKey**, an API key used for authentication and access control. The methods associated with this endpoint are **receiveDocuments()** and **receiveDocumentsInAdvance()**.

The **response** represents the standardized response structure returned by the API Reference Model, containing status, message, and data information in API responses. Its attributes are **status**, an integer representing the status code of the response, **message**, a string providing a descriptive message related to the response status, and **data**, the document containing specific data relevant to the operation.

The **Classes for Data Elements** represent specific details essential for managing logistic operations, which include **document**, **transportModal**, **transportOperation**, **transportUndertaking**, **datetime**, **organization**, **point**, **route**, **driver**, **vehicle**, and **load**. Each class encapsulates various attributes and methods that define their respective data elements. Each class's attributes provide specific details such as IDs, names, statuses, and other relevant parameters important for logistic operations.

In summary, the technical specifications and interoperability considerations highlight the API's dedication to making data exchange in the logistic sector efficient and standardized. By following industry best practices and standards, the API Reference Model becomes a pillar for promoting interoperability and collaboration among stakeholders.

The following table provides a detailed UML diagram description that defines the components of the API Reference Model we saw at a high level in the previous figure. Each row represents a class, which is a fundamental building block of the model. The Type column categorizes the class as either an API or a Data

Element, indicating whether it handles communication or represents data structures. The Attributes column lists the properties of each class, describing the specific information it stores (e.g., id, type, authorization). The Methods column outlines the actions or functions the class can perform, such as receiveDocuments() or updateDocuments(), which define how in essence the API interacts with data and stakeholders.

Table 3. UML Diagram Description

Class	Type	Description	Attributes	Methods
API	API	The main interface of the API. Coordinates communication between organizations and authorities for data exchange.	- organizationEndpoint - authorityEndpoint	- receiveDocuments() : response - provideDocuments() : response - receiveDocumentsInAdvance() : response - provideDocumentsInAdvance() : response - updateDocuments() : response - deleteDocuments() : response
organizationEndpoint	API	The endpoint for organization-related requests. Facilitates organizations in receiving and providing documents to and from the API.	- id: string - apiKey: string	- receiveDocuments() - provideDocuments() - provideDocumentsInAdvance() - updateDocuments() : response - deleteDocuments() : response
authorityEndpoint	API	The endpoint for authority-related requests. Facilitates authorities to receive documents from operators through the API.	- id: string - apiKey: string	- receiveDocuments() - receiveDocumentsInAdvance()
response	API	The response returned by the API. Contains status, message, and data information in API responses.	- status: int - message: string - data: document	- None
document	Data Element	The fields of the provided document. Contains detailed information about the transportation.	- transportModal: transportModal - transportOperation: transportOperation - transportUndertaking: transportUndertaking - datetime: datetime - organization: organization - point: point - route: route - driver: driver - vehicle: vehicle - load: load	- None

transportModal	Data Element	Information about the mode of transportation, which stores the type of the transportation (Monomodal or Multimodal), and the transportation phase.	- type: string - phase: integer	- None
transportOperation	Data Element	Information about the transportation operation, which stores the type of the operation (Cabotage, Cross-trade, Occasional or Regular) and its id.	- id: integer - type: string	- None
transportUndertaking	Data Element	Information about the transport undertaking, which stores the authorization to engage in a profession and to operate on the market, good repute, risk score, and professional competence.	- authorization: string - goodRepute: string - riskScore: string - professionalCompetence:string	- None
datetime	Data Element	Information about the operational date and time in the format YYYYMMDD and HH:MM:SS respectively	- operationalDate: date - operationalTime: time	- None
organization	Data Element	Information about the organization, which stores the organization name, professional competence, and authorization to perform transport operations.	- name: string - professionalCompetence: string - authorization: string	- None
point	Data Element	Information about the starting and stopping points of the logistic operation (e.g.	- startingPoint: string - stoppingPoint: string	- None

		Rotterdam, Novara).		
route	Data Element	Information about the type of route (e.g. road, rail, sea, air) and its id.	- id: integer - type: string	- None
driver	Data Element	Information about the driver, which stores the driver id, name, professional competence, authorization to perform transport operations, driving record, and working/resting times.	- id: integer - name: string - professionalCompetence: string - authorization: string - drivingRecord: string - workingTimes: string - restingTimes: string	- None
vehicle	Data Element	Information about the vehicle, which stores the vehicle id, type, plate, technical condition, weight, dimensions, registration, conformity, and required inspections.	- id: integer - type: string - plate: string - technicalCondition: string - weight: double - dimensions: string - registration: string - conformity: string - requiredInspections: string	- None
load	Data Element	Information about the load/goods, which stores the type of goods, authorization for carrying specific goods, and cargo securing.	- typeOfGoods: string - authorization: string - cargoSecuring: string	- None

8.3 Use Cases Integration

The integration of use cases within the API Reference Model demonstrates the practical application of its functionalities in real-world logistic scenarios. The API Reference Model serves as the foundational blueprint for creating the API Standard, which will later be implemented in Task 2.3, and also be developed as a Python library hosted in GitHub to also address the needs of the web app. Valuable insights into the complexities of multimodal and monomodal transportation and varied interactions between stakeholders and systems are gained through the analysis of two distinct use cases from Task 1.4. These use cases showcase how the API Standard, developed from the API Reference Model, will address key logistics challenges and support efficient data exchange.

Figure 8 Use Cases

Firstly, a scenario involving multimodal transportation, which utilizes different modes of transport, such as rail and road, is explored. In this scenario, an intermodal rail shipment originating from a port is forwarded by rail to an inland terminal, where it undergoes last-mile transportation by road. At this point, the organization provides documents to the enforcement authority. A sequence diagram illustrates the process wherein the enforcer receives the documents in real-time. This use case highlights the API's capability to handle complex logistics operations involving multiple transport modes and stakeholders, ensuring efficient and accurate document exchange.

Figure 9 Sequence Diagram on Use Case 1

Conversely, the second scenario focuses on a monomodal shipment predominantly utilizing road transport. Here, enforcement authorities like port authorities are involved, where documents are provided in advance. A sequence diagram illustrates the pre-notification process, followed by real-time document provision and enforcer acknowledgment. This scenario demonstrates the API's effectiveness in streamlining document exchanges in simpler, yet equally important, logistics operations.

Figure 10 Sequence Diagram on Use Case 2

The sequence diagrams provide a visual representation of the interaction between the organizations and the enforcement authorities, illustrating the flow of information and the exchange of documents. These diagrams also highlight the API Standard's ability to simplify processes, reduce complexity, and ensure the timely availability of relevant information. They also emphasize how the API Standard can be implemented across diverse logistics scenarios, demonstrating its flexibility and scalability.

The practical integration of the API Standard into the use cases demonstrates its potential to streamline logistics operations, improve interoperability, and foster collaboration among stakeholders. By addressing interoperability challenges and facilitating seamless document exchange, the API Standard will enhance the efficiency of logistics operations and enable data-driven decision-making.

In conclusion, the API Reference Model acts as the blueprint for the creation of the API Standard, which will be also implemented as a Python library to provide standardized APIs for seamless data exchange in the logistics sector. The API Standard, built upon this model, ensures interoperability and efficiency across diverse systems and stakeholders. By integrating the API Standard into real-world use cases, we can demonstrate its effectiveness in improving logistics operations and streamlining data exchange. Furthermore, the API Standard will be designed to be flexible and scalable, allowing for future extensions and adaptations as new use cases emerge or existing ones evolve. The Python library that will be developed in Task 2.3 will be open, modular, and user-friendly, making it easy for future enhancements and for a wide range of stakeholders to adopt and build upon. This approach ensures that the API Standard remains a key enabler of a more interconnected, efficient, and future-proof logistics ecosystem.

9. Conclusions

Task 2.1 has effectively built upon the foundational work conducted in WP1, producing an API Reference Model that addresses the needs and challenges identified through extensive research and stakeholder consultation. The task began with a comprehensive literature review of relevant projects and technological advancements, such as DTLF, FEDeRATED, FENIX, and eFTI. Consultations with partners involved in the eFTI4EU project provided firsthand insights regarding the advancements and implications of the eFTI Platforms and Gates' creation, consultations with FENIX and FEDeRATED consortium partners provided firsthand knowledge on their challenges and developments, while investigations into eID authentication mechanisms ensured that security and safety concerns of stakeholders were prioritized.

The analysis of different types of APIs, informed by expert consultations and comparative studies, highlighted the most suitable API type for achieving interconnectivity among logistics and enforcement stakeholders. Drawing lessons from the FEDeRATED project's node configurations and backend APIs, the task outlined an API model that fosters collaboration and addresses the digitalization gaps identified in WP1.

Moreover, Task 2.1 explored the Plug-and-Play Framework, consulting DTLF and FEDeRATED experts and technical partners to understand its theoretical and practical implications. This analysis informed the development of a standardized, interoperable API model designed to facilitate seamless data exchange across diverse platforms used by logistic operators, enforcement authorities, and other stakeholders.

The API Reference Model created through this task incorporates the needs and requirements of stakeholders, the mapped platforms, and applications used across EU Member States, as they were identified and thoroughly investigated in the context of WP1. It aligns with realistic use cases and transaction scenarios, as outlined in T1.4 and will be further elaborated in WP4, ensuring that the API Reference Model is practical and applicable in real-world contexts. This model serves as a blueprint for the subsequent development of the API standard in Task T2.3 and provides crucial input for related tasks and work packages within the KEYSTONE project.

Through extensive literature review, expert consultations, and iterative development, Task 2.1 has established a robust foundation for a standardized digital logistics ecosystem. The strong relationships built with key stakeholders and experts, including DTLF, FEDeRATED, EU MOVE HUB, IMI, EUCARIS, NAPCORE, FENIX, and others, reinforce the credibility and applicability of the API Reference Model. These efforts ensure that the forthcoming API standard will be well-informed, secure, and capable of enhancing data exchange efficiency, transparency, and collaboration within the logistic sector.

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